

Deliverable 6.1

Legal and ethical inventory and in-depth analysis

Date

December 2018

Responsible Partners

KU Leuven

Authors

Erik Kamenjasevic
Elisabetta Biasin

Dissemination Level

Public

Editors

Erik Kamenjasevic
Elisabetta Biasin

Document History

Version	Date	Contributor	Comments
1.0	01.05.2018	Elisabetta Biasin, Erik Kamenjasevic	First outline
1.1	11.06.2018	Elisabetta Biasin, Erik Kamenjasevic	Continuous input
1.2	28.10 – 22.11.2018	ALL partners	DPIA contribution from all partners
1.4	06.12.2018	Prof. Anton Vedder	Document review
1.5	13.12.2018	Barbara Kieslinger	Document review
1.6	14.12.2018	Elisabetta Biasin, Erik Kamenjasevic	Final editing
1.7	16.12.2018	Marta Savoldelli	Document review
1.8	17.12.2018	Erik Kamenjasevic Elisabetta Biasin	Document review and implementation of reviewer's comments
2.0	18.12.2018	Erik Kamenjasevic Elisabetta Biasin	Final document submitted to project coordinator
2.1	27.12.2018	Barbara Kieslinger	Final editing

CONTENTS

CONTENTS	3
List of abbreviations	5
Executive summary	6
1 Introduction	6
1.1 Purpose of the document	6
1.2 Structure of the document	7
2 The privacy and data protection legal framework	7
2.1 Introduction	8
2.2 The ethical and legal framework concerning privacy and data protection	8
2.2.1 The rights to privacy and data protection	8
2.3 Privacy and data protection in Europe: overview of the legal framework	9
2.3.1 The General Data Protection Regulation and the actual framework	10
2.3.2 The e-Privacy Directive	11
2.3.3 Key definitions of data protection law	12
2.4 Key principles and rules of data protection law	19
2.4.1 Key principles relating to the processing of personal data.....	19
2.4.2 Lawful grounds for the processing of personal data	22
2.4.3 Security of processing.....	26
2.4.4 Accountability and promotion of compliance	26
2.4.5 Data Protection by Design	28
2.4.6 Rights of data subjects.....	29
2.5 Key data protection legal requirements and recommendations for Made4You	30
2.5.1 Introduction	30
2.5.2 Participation of individuals within the Made4You Project	31
2.5.3 Possible lawful grounds for the processing of personal data	32
2.5.4 Further technical and organisational measures	33
2.6 Key data protection legal requirements and recommendations for Careables platform	36
2.6.1 Introduction	36
2.6.2 The principle of data protection by design	36
2.6.3 The handling of personal data within Careables	41
2.6.4 The role of consent within the Careables scenario	42
2.6.5 Provision of information to data subjects	43
2.6.6 Effectiveness of the exercise of data subjects' rights	44
2.6.7 Further technical and organisational measures	45
3 IPRs framework	45
3.1 Introduction	45
3.2 Copyright.....	46
3.2.1 About the copyright protection in general	46
3.2.2 Overview of the EU Copyright Framework	47
3.3 Open Source Software	50
3.3.1 Open vs. proprietary software.....	51
3.3.2 OSS license.....	51

3.4	Creative Commons Licenses.....	52
3.4.1.	About CC licenses	54
3.5	Patent rights.....	57
3.6	Open Source Hardware.....	58
4	<i>Made4You, Careables and implications concerning Liability.....</i>	60
4.1	Introduction	60
4.1.1.	Contract law.....	60
4.1.2.	Tort law.....	60
4.1.3.	Product Liability Law.....	61
4.2	DIY environments and DIY ‘simple’ devices.....	62
4.2.1.	What liability?.....	62
4.3	DIY environments and Medical Devices	65
4.3.1.	DIY and objects falling under the definition of ‘Medical Devices’	65
4.3.2.	The legal framework concerning Medical Devices	66
4.3.3.	What Liability?	68
5	<i>Ethical Guidelines.....</i>	70
5.1	Introduction	70
5.2	Fundamental moral principles	70
5.3	Ethical issues addressed through and beyond the legal framework.....	72
5.3.1.	A brief introduction	72
5.3.2.	Examples of ethical issues addressed through the legal framework.....	72
5.3.3.	Examples of ethical issues addressed beyond the legal framework.....	72
6	<i>Conclusions</i>	73
7	<i>Bibliography.....</i>	74
	<i>Annex I - Inventory of key data protection principles and guidelines</i>	77
	<i>Annex II – Report of Data Protection Impact Assessments carried out in the context of Made4You</i>	81

List of abbreviations

CC	Creative Commons
Convention 108	The Convention for the Protection of Individuals with the regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data
DPA	Data Protection Authority
DPD	Data Protection Directive
DPO	Data Protection Officer
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
ECHR	European Convention on Human Rights
EDPB	European Data Protection Board
EDPS	European Data Protection Supervisor
FRA	European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
MDD	Medical Devices Directives
OSHL	open source hardware licensing
OSSL	open source software licensing
TFEU	Treaty of Functioning of the European Union
WP29	Article 29 Working Party

Tables index

Table 1: Personal data	13
Table 2: Data concerning health.....	15
Table 3: Consent requirements	24
Table 4: DPIA requirements.....	35
Table 5: Academic license vs. Copyleft license	51
Table 6: From the licensor's point of view	53
Table 7: From the licensee's point of view, when you use any Creative Commons work	54
Table 8: Patent vs. Copyright.....	57

Figures index

Figure 1: Consent Process	31
Figure 2: PRIPARE's lightweight itinerary	38

Executive summary

Careables.org has a goal of becoming an online platform that will serve as a central hub for sharing knowledge for reproduction and self-creation of customized healthcare solutions. It will encompass repository for the storage of projects' technical documentation and it shall represent an environment where individuals with particular needs, healthcare professionals, makers, designers, donors and co-founders work collaboratively online in order to create custom-made healthcare solutions – careables¹. In order to develop a platform that respects all the applicable legal and ethical requirements, this deliverable is focusing on the following topics: privacy and data protection, intellectual property legal framework, liability and medical devices, and ethics. Requirements stemming from these legislations are to be seen as the crucial ones for successful development of the platform. In particular, privacy and data protection legislation will become relevant mainly when the abovementioned stakeholders interact via the platform. The overarching principle of accountability has to be followed without exception and privacy by design approach is studied extensively in order to have it implemented in the platform itself from its early stage of the development. Further on, intellectual property legal framework is relevant for the solutions that will be uploaded on the platform. The EU copyright system grants exclusive rights to the author of a copyrighted work as soon as such work is created. At the same time, the goal and aspiration of the Made4You Consortium is to enable as many people as possible to use and replicate 'freely' the careables published on the platform. Therefore, this deliverable provides an overview of the alternative systems (that may be summarised in "some rights reserved") to the traditional IP approach. In that regard, open source software and hardware, and creative commons systems were researched in order to provide an overview of the legal requirements for careables developers. The subsequent section deals with the issue of liability that may arise with regard to the co-design, development and reproduction of the careables. The main finding and the general rule states that liability for defective products concerning DIY solutions becomes apparent only when the defendant made such solution in the course of business or the solution is industrially produced. Moreover, current and soon to be applicable legal framework concerning medical devices has been studied. To this end, apart from establishing whether the DIY solutions fall under the notion of 'medical device' under the new Regulation, the platform will not be considered as manufacturer as long as it does not "put devices on the market". Finally, the last chapter 5 deals with ethics. It supplements all the previous chapters by studying fundamental ethical principles that may be used as a support for stakeholders to ensure protection and advancement of human values as well as guidance for the interpretation of the law.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

The purpose of the deliverable D6.1 is twofold. First, this deliverable aims at drawing the legal and ethical inventory comprising all relevant ethical and legal requirements, and to provide an advice to the Consortium partners concerning the fundamental legal requirements in order

¹ Definition of a "careable" is currently under development by the Made4You Consortium partners.

to ensure their implementation already at the early stage of the project development. To that end, data protection impact assessments have been carried out (see Annex II to this document) by all Consortium partners that are processing personal data for the defined purposes. In particular, the document provides specific report on how to implement privacy and data protection by design principles within the Careables platform. Second, this deliverable provides an in-depth analysis of legal and ethical questions with regard to data protection, product responsibility and torts in the sector of medical devices, management of intellectual property rights, open source licensing, and ethical principles that need to be taken into account when dealing with Careables.

1.2 Structure of the document

Deliverable D6.1 is divided into 5 main chapters. It starts with the Introduction and general overview of the document. Chapter 2 deals with the privacy and data protection framework. Within this chapter, two main legislative documents were taken into account, namely General Data Protection Regulation and the so-called e-Privacy Directive. Chapter 3 deals with the IPRs framework where two relevant intellectual property rights were studied; copyright and patent rights. However, the aim of the Made4You Consortium is to document Careables that are as open as possible. In other words, Consortium's aspiration is not to have "all rights reserved" approach of the product developers but "some rights reserved" or even "none rights reserved". Therefore, in order to facilitate achievement of this goal, D6.1 provides an extensive overview of legislation that concerns open source software, open source hardware, and creative commons. In Chapter 4, the analysis of applicable legislation is done towards liability concerning the co-design, development and reproduction of Careables. Therefore, the chapter covers relevant legal notions stemming from contract law, tort law, product liability law and it focuses specifically on the DIY – medical and non-medical – devices. Finally, Chapter 5 provides an overview of ethical principles applicable within eHealth requirements that should not be overlooked while dealing with Careables. Hence, this chapter focuses on the fundamental moral principles as well as it deals with the ethical issues addressed through and beyond legal framework.

2 The privacy and data protection legal framework

This Section outlines the main legal and ethical requirement for Made4You with respect to the framework of privacy and data protection legislation. Section 2.1 provides a general introduction to the privacy and data protection legal framework, Section 2.2. outlines the main aspects of privacy and data protection, Section 2.3. is devoted to the illustration of privacy and data protection laws and its key concepts, Section 2.4 provides an overview of the principles and rules of data protection law. After such preliminary outline, Section 2.5 contains a description of the main data protection legal requirements to be evaluated and taken into account by Consortium partners in the whole context of the Made4You project, whereas Section 2.6 explains the main legal requirements specifically for the development of the Made4You platform 'Careables'.

2.1 Introduction

Made4You is a H2020 project whose scope it to create a central hub for citizens to share knowledge for the reproduction or self-creation of customised healthcare solutions. Its intention is to offer a platform ('Careables') for sharing knowledge concerning healthcare solutions thanks to the interaction between different users/stakeholders. The subjects to be involved as users/stakeholders in the project and in the platform environment will be:

- Individuals with healthcare needs and their caregivers;
- Healthcare professionals;
- Makers, designers, engineers and developers;
- Donors, co-funders, crowd funders.

The platform aims at representing the environment for the sharing of knowledge for the co-design of healthcare solutions. It will consists of a repository for the storage of projects' documentation (including but not limited to files, design description, assembly guides and bills of materials, videos of the process, brief interviews to developers) and will aim to constitute an environment where the above mentioned stakeholders will be able to work collaboratively online for the design, creation, development of healthcare solutions (e.g. by allowing them to share, improve, comment on technical documentation and more widely, to contribute to their respective projects). The creation, development and therefore the existence itself of a platform where the above-mentioned actors/stakeholders will have access and will interact together is likely to entail the processing of personal data (as well as 'sensitive data' (§2.3.3.2). Also, as parallel and complementary activity, Consortium partners will promote the engagement of communities of different stakeholders by bringing them together on a local and global level through the organisation of *ad hoc* events, gatherings, meetings, etc. Such activities may imply as well the processing of personal data of the involved individuals. Therefore, it is obvious that the respect of privacy and data protection laws are of key importance for the lawfulness of this initiative and their legal requirements must be taken into account as of the early stage of the project.

2.2 The ethical and legal framework concerning privacy and data protection

Given the characteristics and functions of Made4You implying the processing of users' and stakeholders' personal data, the project has to be carried out by taking into account the legal requirements foreseen by privacy and data protection laws, following at the same time a solid and consistent ethical approach. To such purpose, this section provides an overview of the applicable legal framework with respect to privacy and data protection. The illustration of such framework is preliminary to identify the main requirements to take into account for Made4You.

2.2.1. The rights to privacy and data protection

The framework concerning privacy and data protection is heterogeneous and it is composed by a multitude of sources. Such multitude is due to the inner nature of the matter of regulation – technology – which is constantly under change.

Three decades ago, the ‘right to privacy’ and ‘the right to data protection’ had a different meaning with respect to the broader meaning they have assumed today. The evolution of technology has implied a change to these concepts and has required the constant evolution of the respective legal scenario. In legal literature discussions have been made concerning the distinction between the right to privacy and the right to data protection. Such distinction is also due to the historical affirmation of such rights into International and European legal landscape² and the interpretation thereof by the competent authorities.

To summarise an extensive debate in literature, even if closely related, the ‘right to privacy’ and ‘the right to data protection’ are distinct rights. They both protect similar values, i.e. the autonomy and human dignity of individuals and strive to preserve individuals’ personal sphere in which they can develop their personalities and shape their opinion. However, the ‘right to privacy’ and the ‘right to data protection’ are different, in their formulation and scope. The first consist in a general prohibition of interference, subject to some public interest criteria that can justify interference in certain cases. The second is perceived as a modern and active right³, coming into relevance whenever occurs the processing of personal data. To this regard, it perceives as necessary to build a system of checks and balances for the protection of individuals when their data are processed and thus asks for the compliance with the essential components of personal data protection. Having such premised – without the purposes of providing an extensive overview of the evolution of the concepts of the rights to privacy and data protection in legal doctrine – for the scope of the execution of Made4You project, a pragmatic approach to law prevails and the protection of the right to privacy and the protection to the right to data protection are considered of equal importance. This choice is made in order to provide a pragmatically oriented guidance to the Consortium in the matter of privacy and data protection. Following such approach, the following section provides a brief overview of the applicable privacy and data protection legal framework, having regard to list the relevant sources and documents that may be of major impact for Made4You.

2.3 Privacy and data protection in Europe: overview of the legal framework

The applicable framework concerning the field of privacy and data protection in EU is composed by a multitude of legal sources to be taken into account. Since their early foundations until today, the matter of privacy and data protection has known a process of evolution in its regulation.

The primary sources of the privacy and data protection legal framework are represented by the Treaty on the Functioning of the EU⁴ (TFEU) and the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (the Charter). Due to the obligations posed from the above mentioned sources, the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR) of the Council of Europe is also of a high importance, as well as the Convention for the Protection of Individuals with the regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data (commonly referred to as ‘Convention 108’). As a source of secondary EU law (but not of less importance) is Regulation (EU) 2016/679,

² FRA, Handbook on European data protection law, 2018 edition, Chapter 1.

³ CJEU, Joined cases C-92/09 and C-93, Volker und Markus Schecke GbR v Land Hessen, Opinion of Advocate General Sharpston, 17 June 2010, para. 71.

⁴ Treaty on European Union and the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union, 2012/C 326/01.

commonly known as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)⁵, that entered into force as of May 2018 and repealed the Directive 95/46/CE⁶. The GDPR – likewise for the former Directive – is subject to the interpretative guidance provided by the relevant Data Protection Authorities (DPAs) and Bodies at European and national level and national laws and regulations may implement and further specify the requirements set by the same selves. Also, national and non-national Court decisions may be relevant for the interpretation of the principles and rules foreseen by privacy and data protection law. Therefore, all the mentioned documents, recommendations and decisions will be taken into account throughout this deliverable to the extent it is necessary and relevant.

For the purposes of Made4You, the following documents pertaining to the privacy and data protection framework will be discussed extensively:

- 1) The General Data Protection Regulation;
- 2) The Convention for the Protection of Individuals with the regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data, commonly referred to as Convention 108⁷;
- 3) The OECD privacy principles⁸;
- 4) Opinions, guidelines and recommendations provided by Data Protection Bodies and Authorities.

2.3.1. The General Data Protection Regulation and the actual framework

Before 2018, the principal EU legal instrument regulating data protection was Directive 95/46/CE (known also as ‘Data Protection Directive’, hereinafter also ‘DPD’). Adopted in 1995, the Directive aimed at harmonising the data protection legal framework of all EU member states with a set of detailed and comprehensive rules. The Data Protection Directive reflected the data protection principles contained in Convention 108 and added further instruments concerning the protection of data subjects’ personal data.

The rules foreseen by DPD – according to the EU legal system – were not directly applicable, as they had to be transposed into the national law of each Member State. For this cause, even if the legal canvas of legislation among EU member states was common, the national laws transposing the Directive presented elements of differentiation. In a wider perspective it was noticeable an heterogeneous situation for the data protection legal frameworks among Member States, in which definitions and rules were interpreted differently from one Member State to another. Further on, in 2009 a process for the modernization of the legal framework began due to the necessity to adopt a common and directly applicable set of rules for the protection of personal data in Europe, and due to the necessity to align the legal framework to the recent technology developments. After five years of intense discussions, in April 2016 the General Data Protection Regulation was adopted. The General Data Protection Regulation (hereinafter also ‘the Regulation’ or ‘GDPR’) became directly applicable on 25 May 2018 in all Member States. Differently from the Directive, the Regulation is by nature directly applicable, it has

⁵ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European parliament and of the council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation).

⁶ Directive 95/46/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 October 1995 on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data

⁷ Council of Europe (CoE), Convention for the Protection of Individuals with regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data, 28.I.1981.

⁸ OECD Guidelines on the Protection of Privacy and Transborder Flows of Personal Data, 2018.

not to be transposed into the national legislation of each Member State. However, it must be noted that for determined cases and matters, the Regulation left open room for national laws to further set out specific rules, depending of the peculiarities of determined matters to be set by each national regulation (for instance labour law, health law). Following the path of DPD, the GDPR has updated the EU data protection legal framework. It preserved and developed the core principles set by the DPD and at the same time it has further foreseen new requirements for the protection of personal data. In the paragraphs below will be provided an outline of the GDPR key principles (§2.4) as well as the main data protection requirements that will have to be considered for purposes of the Made4You project (§2.4, §2.5) .

2.3.2. The e-Privacy Directive

The provisions foreseen in the former DPD and then in the GDPR are intended to apply ‘horizontally’ to all sectors. In the early 2000s, however, it was deemed necessary to establish specific data protection rules in the sector of electronic communications, in order to regulate the internet environment and to provide rules for the respect of users’ right to privacy and confidentiality. **Directive 2002/58/EC**⁹ concerning the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in electronic communications’ integrates the mentioned data protection horizontal framework by providing rules, *inter alia*, on the security of personal data and confidentiality of communications. The e-privacy Directive mainly contains obligations for electronic communications service providers. At the same time, it includes a provision concerning unsolicited communications and contains rules on the **storage of cookies** on devices. According to Art. 5(3) e-Privacy Directive, Member States have to ensure that “the storing of information, or the gaining of access to information already stored, in the terminal equipment of a subscriber or user is only allowed on condition that the subscriber or user concerned has given his or her consent, having been provided with clear and comprehensive information, in accordance with Directive 95/46/EC, *inter alia*, about the purposes of the processing”. Such requirement does not apply to “technical storage or access for the sole purpose of carrying out the transmission of a communication over an electronic communications network, or as strictly necessary in order for the provider of an information society service explicitly requested by the subscriber or user to provide the service” (*ibid.*). Due to the nature of the Directive – requiring national transposition in each Member State of the EU – its implementation has varied across Europe (thus leading to heterogeneous interpretations of the rules on cookie storage). On 2013, WP29 issued a Working Paper¹⁰ providing guidance on obtaining consent for cookies. Further analysis and guidance concerning this argument for the purposes of the Careables platform is provided under (§2.6.4.2).

2.3.2.1. E-Privacy reforms

As of January 2017, there has been proposed a draft EU Regulation to replace the e-Privacy Directive, with the aim to be – analogously to the GDPR – directly applicable among all the EU

⁹ Directive 2002/58/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 July 2002 concerning the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in the electronic communications, OJ L201 (hereinafter: ‘e-Privacy Directive’).

¹⁰ WP29, Working Document 02/2013 providing guidance on obtaining consent for cookies, WP208, adopted on 2 October 2013 (hereinafter: ‘Working Document on obtaining consent for cookies’).

Member States.¹¹ Objective of the reform is to align the existing framework on privacy and electronic communications with GDPR, thus providing users greater control over their electronic communications. Among the many novelties, the reform proposes to extend the scope of application of rules on e-privacy to cover not only ‘traditional’ service providers (e.g. voice telephony, text messages and electronic mail conveyance services), but also ‘over-the-top’ (OTT) internet-based communication services, such as Voice over IP, messaging services and web-based email services. The e-privacy Regulation, once it enters into force (most likely not before the year 2020) may imply changes on the requirements concerning cookies. The proposed changes to the current rules, once approved by EU legislative bodies, may therefore imply an impact on the Careables platform.

2.3.3. Key definitions of data protection law

Preliminarily to the analysis of the framework and the descending legal requirements it is necessary to outline the key definitions of data protection law. This explanation will serve as the basic premise for the analysis of specific topics in the sections that will follow.

2.3.3.1. *Personal data*

The term ‘personal data’ is defined in Art. 4(1) GDPR. According to this, personal data is “any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person” (the ‘data subject’). The Regulation explains that “an identifiable natural person can be identified in a direct or indirect way, for instance by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person”.

In order to establish whether ‘data’ could be considered as ‘personal’ it is therefore necessary to evaluate the following three elements of the legal definition: 1) “any information” 2) “relating to”; 3) “an identified or identifiable natural person”¹².

The expression ‘*any information*’ suggests a wide interpretation of the concept and implies that the nature or content of the information as well as the technical format in which it is presented it is not relevant. Objective and subjective information about a person may be considered as personal data.

‘*Relating to*’: information can be considered as relating to an individual when it is about that individual. In many situations, this relationship can be easily established (e.g. the data on the results of a patient’s medical test contained in his medical records). In situations where it is less evident whether an information may relate to an individual, three additional alternative criteria may be taken into consideration:

- The ‘content’: information relates to the person when it is *about* that person. For instance, the results of a medical analysis clearly relate to the patient (the data is clearly about Titius);

¹¹ Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council concerning the respect for private life and the protection of personal data in electronic communications and repealing Directive 2002/58/EC, COM(2017) 10, 10 January 2010.

¹² Cfr. Article 29 Data Protection Working Party (hereinafter: ‘WP29’), Opinion 4/2007 on concept of personal data, adopted on 20 June 2007.

- The ‘purpose’: information relates to the person when the data are used or likely to be used with the purpose to evaluate, treat in a certain way or influence the status or behaviour of an individual. For instance, telephone call logs inside a company may be associated to certain data subjects as they may be brought into relation with these in different ways (the data will be used in order to treat Titius in a certain way);
- The ‘result’: data relate to an individual if their use is likely to have an impact on a certain person’s rights and interests. For instance, the localisation of taxi vehicles are to be considered as personal data as the use of such information may be used to evaluate the performance of taxi drivers, to check the respect of rules etc. (the data is likely to have an impact on the rights and interests of Titius).

‘An identified or identifiable person’: a natural person can be considered ‘identified’ when, considered within a group of persons he or she is ‘distinguished’ from all other members of the group. A natural person can be considered as ‘identifiable’ when, although not identified, it is *possible* to do it, in a direct or indirect way. The identification of an individual may also depend on the context in which occurs the processing of the data and by the means that can be used to identify the natural person. To ascertain whether the means are reasonable to be used to identify the natural person, all objective factors should be examined (such as the costs of and the amount required for identification), taking into consideration the available technology at the time of the processing and in the light of technological developments.

When a given information does not allow the identification of an individual, data protection requirements are not applicable. This is the case for anonymised data (for a more in-depth overview of the notion of anonymised and pseudonymised data see below, §2.3.3.3, §2.3.3.4).

The table below provides practical examples of what kind information can be considered personal data:

Table 1: Personal data

- Full name
- Home address
- Photos
- Videos
- Email address
- A person’s social media account and the related posts
- Connection data (IP address, event logs, etc.)
- Location data (GPS data, GSM data, etc.)

2.3.3.2. *Special categories of personal data*

Certain categories of personal data are recognized by law to be more ‘sensitive’ and therefore higher levels of protection is accorded to these with respect to ‘common’ personal data. There are many categories of personal data that the law considers as ‘special’. In particular, data concerning health (hereinafter also: ‘health data’) are considered as such.

‘**Data concerning health**’ are defined in Art. 4(15) and Recital 35 of the GDPR as personal data related to the physical or mental health of a natural person which reveal information about his or her past, current or future health status. The notion includes any information that may be collected in the course of the registration for, or the provision of, health care services; any number, symbol or particular assigned to a natural person to uniquely identify the natural person for health purposes; any information derived from the testing or examination of a body part or bodily substance, including from genetic data and biological samples; and any information on, for example, a disease, disability, disease risk, medical history, clinical treatment or the physiological or biomedical state of the data subject – independent of its source, for example from a physician or other health professional, a hospital, a medical device or an in vitro diagnostic test. As outlined in different occasions by EU Bodies¹³, a wide range of personal data may fall into the category of health data¹⁴:

- **Medical data** have been uniformly considered as ‘health data’. These are all information concerning the physical or mental health status of a data subject that are generated in a professional medical context. The notion includes all data related to contacts with individuals and their diagnosis or treatment by providers of health services, any information related to diseases, disabilities, history of an individual. Also, irrespective of whether they are considered as ‘medical devices’, also **data generated by devices or apps** used in this professional medical context may be considered ‘medical data’.
- **Health related data**: Also data that are not strictly qualifiable as ‘medical data’ may relate to the health status of a person. Examples in European case law and soft law are many. For instance, the information that a woman has a broken leg and is working half-time on a medical ground has been considered as a health data.¹⁵ Further cases have been outlined by WP29, e.g.: the information that a person wears contact lenses, the information about smoking and drinking habits, any data concerning intellectual or emotional capacity of a person, data used in administrative contexts such as data concerning individuals with specific diseases or disabilities for obtaining allowances (such as tax reduction purposes), etc.¹⁶

¹³ See e.g. WP29, Advice paper on special categories of data (“sensitive data”), April 2011; WP29, Annex to Letter from the WP29 to the European Commission, DG CONNECT on mHealth, 5 February 2015.

¹⁴ Concerning the notion of health data, it is important to underline that specific legal requirements concerning health data may vary among EU Member State. To this regard, see Art. 9(4) GDPR: “Member States may maintain or introduce further conditions, including limitations, with regard to the processing of genetic data, biometric data or data concerning health”.

¹⁵ CJEU, C-101/01, Criminal Proceedings against Bodil Lindqvist, 6 November 2013, (see para. 51).

¹⁶ WP29, Annex to Letter from the WP29 to the European Commission, DG CONNECT on mHealth, 5 February 2015, p. 2.

- **Data not per se health related but that allow for health related conclusions after processing:** In certain circumstances, data that in a first moment seem not to be concerning health may be nonetheless categorized as health data. This occurs when data – also collected in aggregated form – is or can be used (in itself or in combination with other data) to draw conclusions about a person’s health status or health risk. When such kind of processing occurs, and it is used to draw conclusions on persons’ health status or health risk, then the processed data are to be considered as health data. An example may be provided with the case of lifestyle apps: a single registration of blood or heart rate without any further information about age or sex does not allow for the inference of information about the health status of a person. Nonetheless, if this aspect is measured over time and it is combined with other data such as age or sex, then it may be used to determine a significant aspect of an individual’s health. It is therefore worth to underline that **data generated by devices** (e.g. devices analysing a person’s blood, apps measuring heart rate, etc.) may be considered as health data, regardless whether the testing is carried out by medical professionals or devices/apps that are available on the market, and irrespective whether these devices are marketed as medical devices or not. Also, to this regard, it should be noted that when the controller combines non-health data with health data in order to better understand the health status of an individual, then all the collected data are to be qualified as health data. It is the case e.g. when a controller is provided by a third party with non-health data and successively processes such data for health-related purposes, such as medical profiling. In this context, even data that outside the medical context would not qualify as personal data may consequently be **qualified as health data, depending on the (health-related) purposes of the data processing.**¹⁷

The table below provides practical examples of what kind of personal data can be considered as ‘data concerning health’:

Table 2: Data concerning health

Medical data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Medical history and clinical treatment data concerning an individual • Heart rate, blood pressure measured by a device or an app in the context of a professional health service
Health related data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data concerning the purchase of medical products, devices and services • Information collected in the context of online questionnaires with the purpose of providing health advice

¹⁷ EDPS, Opinion 1/2015, Mobile Health, Reconciling technological innovation with data protection, 21 May 2015.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Membership of an individual in a patient support group, Alcoholics Anonymous or other self-help support group with a health-related objective • Data on allergies disclosed to private entities (e.g. airlines) or public bodies (e.g. schools)
Data allowing individuals' health status inference	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Heart rate, blood pressure measured by a device or an app (itself or combined with other data) in order to infer an individual health status or health risk or well-being of a person

In principle, the processing of health data is prohibited, unless an exception applies. The rationale behind this enhanced protection of special categories of personal data stems from the presumption that the misuse of these data in general is likely to have more severe consequences for individuals' fundamental rights than the misuse of the other 'less sensitive' data. The misuse of health data may be irreversible and may have serious consequences in the long term for the individual as well as for his or her social context.

2.3.3.3. *Anonymous or anonymised data*

According to the principle of **storage limitation** foreseen in data protection law, data have to be kept "in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the data are processed".¹⁸ Once the retention of data is no longer necessary for the established purposes of the processing, the controller is required to take action through the erasure or the anonymisation of data. The process of anonymisation of data implies that all the identifying elements are eliminated from a data set in order to irreversibly prevent the identification of the individual to which the data are referring to. As outlined above, when data do not allow the identification or identifiability of an individual they may be considered as 'anonymous' and should therefore not to be regarded as personal data – thus implying that GDPR requirements do not apply. If this assumption seems to be burden-mitigating for controllers, it is necessary to underline that the consideration of data as 'anonymous' has not to be taken lightly. In practice, the process for rendering personal data anonymous has become more and more difficult due to technological developments and by consequence the concept of 'anonymised data' has been subject to a strict interpretation in legal doctrine.¹⁹ In 2014, WP29 provided practical guidance²⁰ on different anonymization techniques and acknowledged that certain techniques are more efficient than others which may not be effective in some cases. The overall recommendation provided by WP29 is to **evaluate on a case-by-case basis which technique** (possibly in combination with other techniques) **may be the most effective for the situation**. Controllers should always consider that after the process of anonymization **no element** shall be left in the information which could, by exercising reasonable effort, serve **to re-identify the individual concerned**. Moreover, the risk of re-identification shall be assessed on a continuous basis by the controller. On this point, the GDPR provides that to such purpose, it is necessary to take into account "all objective factors,

¹⁸ Art. 5(1)(e) GDPR.

¹⁹ P. Ohm, Broken promises of privacy: responding to the surprising failure of anonymisation. UCLA law review, 1701-1759, 2010.

²⁰ WP29, Opinion 5/2014 on Anonymisation Techniques, WP216, 10 April 2014.

such as the costs and the amount of time required for identification, taking into consideration the available technology at the time of the processing and technological developments” (Rec. 26).

In Made4You project, controllers (i.e. those Consortium partners that decide on means and purpose of processing of personal data) should evaluate when and how to anonymise personal data, and for instance when the processing is no longer necessary for the established purposes controllers should evaluate whether to anonymise or to erase the data that have been processed.

2.3.3.4. Pseudonymous or pseudonymised data

According to Art. 4(5) GDPR, pseudonymisation is defined as a “processing of personal data in such a manner that the personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, provided that such additional information is kept separately and is subject to technical and organisational measures to ensure that the personal data are not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person”.

In general, pseudonymisation consists in the replacement of one attribute (normally a unique identifier) in a record by another. The linkability of a given dataset with another dataset with the original identity of a data subject is therefore reduced by anonymisation, however, the natural person is still likely to be indirectly identified. For this reason, such technique when applied alone in a dataset will not result in an anonymous dataset. Having such premised, **pseudonymised data** should be considered as **personal data**, especially if by using correspondence lists or algorithms the unidentified data can be traced back to identify individuals. Nonetheless, **pseudonymisation** may be conceived as a useful means to enhance the security of processing. Many GDPR provisions are aimed at encouraging the use of pseudonymisation as technical measure to ensure a level of security appropriate to the risk.²¹ Indeed, as Recital 26 GDPR puts it, “the application of pseudonymisation to personal data can reduce risks to the data subjects concerned and help controllers and processors to meet their data-protection obligations”.

It is recommendable for all Made4You Consortium partners who are processing personal data to consider the pseudonymisation of personal data in order to strengthen the security of the data.

2.3.3.5. Data subject

Under EU law the only beneficiaries of data protection rules are natural persons. Art. 4(1) GDPR states that personal data is “any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person”, which is the data subject. Data subjects are therefore the natural persons/individuals whose related information are processed. As a consequence, the personal data relating to data subjects is subject to data protection rules, as will be more in detail described in the sections that will follow.

Data subjects have specific rights that are set forth by data protection law. Hence, occurring specific circumstances data subjects may be entitled to exercise their rights towards the controller (for a wider overview of data subjects’ right, see §2.4.6.). On the other side, the controller has an obligation to ensure that data subjects may exercise their rights and more generally has an obligation of transparency towards data subjects.

²¹ See e.g. Art. 32(1) GDPR.

In the context of the Made4You platform ‘Careables’, individuals that take part in the project’s initiatives or individuals that register on the platform – subsequently providing information relating to their selves – are to be considered as ‘data subjects’.

2.3.3.6. *Data processing*

Another definition worth to be outlined concerns the notion of ‘data processing’. Any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or on sets of personal data has to be considered as ‘processing’ of personal data. Along with the definition of what constitutes a data processing, art. 4(2) GDPR provides practical examples of what is a ‘data processing’. Recording, organization, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction are operations to be considered as ‘data processing’.

It may be noted that the definition of processing is extremely broad. In relation to Made4You, an example of data processing is represented by the collection, storage and registration of information concerning individuals within the ‘Careables’ platform. Therefore, such operations have to be considered as ‘personal data processing’ within the meaning of the GDPR.

2.3.3.7. *Actors in the processing of personal data: controllers and processors*

The other roles in the processing of personal data – along with the data subject – are controller and processor. These two may be considered as the ‘active actors’ of the processing, whereas the data subject may be instead considered as the ‘passive actor’ of the processing. The first and most important consequence of being considered as ‘controller’ or ‘processor’ is the **legal responsibility** (and hence liability) for the compliance with obligations foreseen by data protection law. Being a ‘controller’ or a ‘processor’ entails different responsibilities and obligations. Moreover, the roles differ one from the another: the **controller** is whoever (natural or legal person) determines – jointly or with others – the *means* and *purposes* of the processing (Art. 4(7) GDPR), whereas the **processor** is whoever (natural or legal person) processes personal data on behalf of the controller (Art. 4(8) GDPR).

The notions of ‘controller’ and ‘processor’ have been subject to discussions in the legal field²², as in practice it may be difficult to distinguish between these roles. In 2010, the WP29 provided clarification and suggested the adoption of a *functional* approach to investigate whether any entity may be identified as a controller or a processor. In summary – and without the purpose to provide an in-depth overview of the mentioned Opinion – the controller is the entity:

- (1) who *determines* the processing, having the power of **decision making** (the ‘control’) regarding the processing;²³

²² See, WP29 Opinion 1/2010 on the concepts of "controller" and "processor", (WP 169); in legal literature among all B. Van Alsenoy, Allocating responsibility among controllers, processors and “everything in between”: the definition of actors and roles in Directive 95/46/EC, in *Computer Law & Security Review* 28 (2012) 25 – 43.

²³ This power of control may be attributed by the law (explicit legal competence), may be implicit (e.g. existing traditional roles that normally imply a certain responsibility will assist in identifying the controller, e.g. the employer with regard to the employees) or may be factual (whereby on the basis of an assessment of factual circumstances, it is possible to determine what party exercises a ‘dominant role’ with respect to the processing).

- (2) who establishes the *purposes* and *means* of the processing in the sense that it has the power to decide the 'why' and the 'how' of a given processing operation.

The controller may exercise its role jointly with other entities. This is the case where **joint controllers** co-exist.

On the other hand, the processor is the entity that:

- (1) is **delegated** by the controller for the execution of the processing;
- (2) may determine only the *means* but not the *purposes* of the processing.

Controllers, joint controllers and processors are tied by the GDPR as the compliance obligations foreseen by the latter are many: for the purposes of this research project and for the set-up and maintenance in the future of Made4You platform, it is of key importance the identification of the different data protection actors/roles.

2.4 Key principles and rules of data protection law

2.4.1. Key principles relating to the processing of personal data

The fundamental principles of data protection have been historically established by Convention 108 and have been successively incorporated within the Data Protection Directive. In the light of the process of reform of the data protection legal framework, these principles concerning the protection of personal data have been consolidated into a new and single set of principles, under art. 5 GDPR.

The principles governing the processing of personal data are:

- **Lawfulness, fairness and transparency:** personal data have to be processed "lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subject" (Art. 5(1)(a) GDPR);
- **Purpose limitation:** personal data have to be collected for "specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes" (Art. 5(1)(b) GDPR);
- **Data minimisation:** personal data shall be "adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed" (Art. 5(1)(c) GDPR);
- **Accuracy:** personal data shall be "accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date" (Art. 5(1)(d) GDPR);
- **Storage Limitation:** personal data shall be "kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the personal data are processed" (Art. 5(1)(e) GDPR). Controllers should establish time limits for erasure of personal data or for a periodic review thereof.
- **Integrity and Confidentiality:** personal data shall be processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the personal data, including protection against unauthorised or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction or damage, using appropriate technical or organisational measures (Art. 5(1)(f) GDPR);

Also, the GDPR has explicitly provisioned the principle of **accountability**. Affirmed in the past in various Opinions and Recommendations of EU data protection Bodies, this principle has been finally foreseen under Art. 5(2) and 24 of the GDPR.

The next Sections will provide a brief outline of the principles listed above.

2.4.1.1. Lawfulness, fairness and transparency

As a general principle of data protection law, personal data must be processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent way in relation to the data subject (Art. 5(1)(a) GDPR). While lawfulness and fairness already figured among the principles in the Data Protection Directive, the principle of transparency has been recently enshrined as a fundamental principle under the GDPR. More specifically the principle may be analysed under three different lenses:

- **‘Lawfulness’**: it entails that processing of personal data can only take place if based on a lawful ground. The principle is further elaborated in other provisions of the GDPR (namely, Arts. 6 - 10 GDPR), providing: the legal basis on which controllers may rely for the processing of personal data (see also below, §2.4.2); conditions for the lawful acquisition of consent; conditions for the processing of special categories of personal data.
- **‘Fairness’**: it governs primarily the relationship between the controller and the data subject. Fairness requires the controller to handle personal data in ways that the individuals would reasonably expect, having regard to the interests and reasonable expectations of data subjects. Processing operations should not be carried out secretly and data subjects should be aware of potential risks of the processing. The operations performed with individuals’ personal data must occur in alignment with the information that has been disclosed to data subjects.
- **‘Transparency’** entails an obligation for the controller to take adequate measures in order to inform data subjects about the processing of their personal data. The principle is ancillary for the provision to individuals of meaningful control over their personal data and thus enables them to exercise their rights. The principle of transparency foresees that the controller has to disclose in a clear, open and easily accessible way the information concerning the processing of personal data of data subjects. Transparency obligations are further substantiated under Arts. 12-14 GDPR.²⁴

2.4.1.2. Purpose limitation

The principle of **purpose limitation** is strongly connected with the principle of transparency and enables as well the predictability and user control over his or her personal data. Hence, when the purpose of processing is sufficiently specific and clear, data subjects know what to expect. The purpose limitation principle requires that:

- The controller must define the purpose of data processing before the processing is started;
- Personal data must be collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes;

²⁴ Further guidance has been provided by WP29, see WP29, Guidelines on transparency under Regulation 2016/679, WP260 rev.01, adopted on 29 November 2017 as last revised and adopted on 11 April 2018.

- Further processing for additional, specified purposes may occur in a manner that is incompatible with the original purpose. It shall not be done in a way that is unexpected, inappropriate or objectionable for the data subject.²⁵

2.4.1.3. *Data minimisation*

The **data minimisation** principle obliges the processing of personal data to be limited to what is necessary to achieve a legitimate purpose. The principle of data minimisation is therefore consequent of the principle of purpose limitation. Personal data must be “adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed” (Art. 5(1)(c) GDPR).

In order to be in line with the data minimisation principles, Made4You partners should **ensure to process only personal data that are limited and relevant to fulfil the identified purpose**. They should also evaluate whether the purposes could be fulfilled with less data or either through anonymisation, if possible, or by pseudonymisation in order to reduce the possibility to attribute data to data subjects.

2.4.1.4. *Accuracy*

According to the **accuracy** principle, the controller must take every reasonable step to ensure that inaccurate personal data are rectified or erased without delay.

Made4You partners should: check the accuracy of data; record its source; and rectify data when not accurate or updated.

The controller should take “every reasonable step” to ensure accuracy. The reasonableness of the measures to be implemented depends on the purposes of the processing operations. Made4You partners should ensure they put in place **processes ensuring the accuracy of processed data**. For instance, Made4You partners processing data concerning health should make sure that such data that have been collected in the past are up-to-date for the purposes e.g. of co-design sessions.

2.4.1.5. *Storage limitation*

The **storage limitation principle** personal data must not be kept for longer than is necessary for the purposes for which they are processed. It implies that, when personal data are no longer needed for the established purposes, they have to be deleted or anonymised.

Depending on the purpose of the processing activity as well as the nature of the data and the context of the processing, the retention period may vary. The GDPR has not established a framework or reference for the retention period of personal data: this must be evaluated by the data controller on a case by case basis.

In order to align with the principle of storage limitation, Made4You Consortium partners, once identified the purpose(s) of data processing they may consider to identify a **data retention policy**. The data retention policy should regulate the period of retention of personal data and the consequent action to be taken once the purposes of the processing have been fulfilled (**anonymisation or erasure** of personal data).

²⁵ See Explanatory Report of Convention 108, para. 49. In order to evaluate the compatibility of further processing, the controller should consider, *inter alia*, the elements outlined by Recital 50 GDPR.

2.4.1.6. Integrity and confidentiality

The **integrity and confidentiality principle** requires the controller to adopt appropriate technical or organisational measures to protect the data against unauthorized or unlawful processing, accidental loss, destruction or damage.

The GDPR foresees that both the controller and the processor when evaluating the adoption of such measures, must take into account “the state of art, the costs of implementation and the nature, scope, context and purpose of processing, as well as the risk of varying likelihood and severity for the rights and freedoms of the data subjects” (Art. 32(1) GDPR). Therefore, **the appropriateness of security measures are determined on a case-by-case basis** – depending on each specific given context – and should be reviewed on a periodic basis. The integrity and confidentiality principle is further substantiated in the GDPR, primarily under Art. 32 GDPR (‘Security of processing’). Also, Arts. 33-34 GDPR concerning personal data breaches and Art. 35 GDPR concerning the Data Protection Impact Assessment (‘DPIA’) are to be regarded as other specifications of the principle.

2.4.1.7. Accountability

Art. 5(2) GDPR enshrines **accountability** as an overarching principle of data protection law. It prescribes that the controller has to be responsible in ensuring compliance with data protection law and consequently to demonstrate compliance. Such provision has represented a fundamental shift in the approach to data protection. Hence, it demands the controller: i) to adopt a *proactive role* in ensuring the protection of personal data through appropriate technical and organisational measures; and ii) to be able to *demonstrate compliance* with data protection legal requirements. Therefore, it is required for the controller to be scrupulous in evaluating and its choices consequently document these in order to prove compliance with the law. The measures that organisations may put in place for the compliance with law are many (see Chapter IV GDPR). These may depend on the risk of processing and the nature of the data. For instance, the ways with which controllers may facilitate compliance are: the record of processing activities, the designation of a Data Protection Officer (‘DPO’) – on a mandatory or voluntary basis; the undertaking of DPIAs, the adherence to approved codes of conduct or certification mechanisms, etc.

A brief overview of the most relevant measures to put in place is provided further below §2.4.4.

2.4.2. Lawful grounds for the processing of personal data

The principle of lawfulness of the processing implies that every processing of personal data must have a legal basis. The legal basis for the processing of personal data are listed under Art. 6 GDPR, which foresees six hypotheses:

- 1) the data subject **consent**;
- 2) the necessity for the performance of a contract with the data subject;
- 3) the necessity of compliance with a legal obligation;
- 4) the protection of vital interests of the data subject or of another natural person;
- 5) (for public bodies) the necessity to perform a task in the public interest;
- 6) the legitimate interest of the controller or of third parties.

Personal data that are considered as ‘sensitive’ are subject to an **additional layer of protection**. Accordingly, art. 9 GDPR foresees that the processing of special categories of personal

data (including **data concerning health**) shall be prohibited unless one of the following conditions applies²⁶:

- a) the data subject has given **explicit consent** to the processing of personal data;
- b) the processing is necessary for controller to meet legal obligations or for the controller and data subject to exercise specific rights in the field of employment law, social security and social protection law;
- c) the processing is necessary to protect the vital interests of a data subject (or another person), and the data subject is physically or legally incapable of giving consent;
- d) the processing carried out by a non-profit organization whose aim is to advance an agenda related to one of the categories of sensitive data;
- e) the data are manifestly made public by the data subject;
- f) the processing is necessary to establish, exercise or defend legal claims;
- g) the processing is necessary for reasons of substantial public interest on the basis of the Union State law;
- h) the processing is necessary for the purposes of preventive or occupational medicine;
- i) the processing is necessary for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes.

Each controller is required to evaluate for each processing activity which lawful basis applies, given the possibility that one or more than one hypothesis may occur.²⁷ Controllers are required to identify and document the lawfulness grounds from the start of the processing activities. If a genuine change in circumstances occurs or it is identifiable a new purpose for the processing, controllers should consider to assess again the ground of the processing activity. For Made4You as a research project and Careables as the result of the research project, a focus on the notions of consent and the specific related requirements is provided under sections 2.6.5.2.1 and 2.6.4.

2.4.2.1. Consent

Consent is one of the lawful grounds basis for the processing of personal data. Traditionally, it has been associated with the idea that the data subject should have the control of the use it is being made with its data. Consent is defined as²⁸ in “any freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous indication of the data subject’s wishes by which he or she, by a statement or by a clear affirmative action, signifies agreement to the processing of personal data relating to him or her”. To be valid, consent has to be freely given, specific, informed, unambiguous

²⁶ It is of key importance to stress again that concerning the processing of sensitive data, art. 9(4) GDPR foresees that “Member States may maintain or introduce further conditions, including limitations, with regard to the processing of genetic data, biometric data or data concerning health”.

²⁷ In order to do so, controllers are required to consider the various factors concerning the processing of personal data. Guidance in this field has been widely provided by EU national Data Protection Authorities (“DPAs”). For instance see: ICO’s ‘Lawful basis interactive guidance tool’, available at <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/resources-and-support/lawful-basis-interactive-guidance-tool/>.

²⁸ Art. 4(11) GDPR.

and – for data concerning health – explicit. These requirements for consent to be valid²⁹ are further illustrated in the table below and correlated with practical examples:

Table 3: Consent requirements

Consent requirements under data protection law	
'Freely given'	Data subjects must be able to make a real choice and exercise a control over their data. If the data subject has no real choice, feels forced to consent or will face negative consequences in case he or she does not consent, then consent will not be considered as valid. <i>Example:</i> A consent bundled as a non-negotiable part of terms and conditions for of a contract or a registration form in a website may not be considered as 'freely given'.
'Specific'	Consent must be given in relation to one or more specific purposes, in order to provide the data subject with the possibility to choose for each of these. To comply with this element, the controller must: (i) adequately specify each of the purposes for which it will carry out the processing; (ii) apply granularity in consent requests, and (iii) separate the information related to the acquisition of consent for data processing activities from information concerning other matters. <i>Example:</i> A unique consent acquired by the controller for different processing purposes may not be considered as specific.
'Informed'	It is fundamental to provide information to the data subject prior to obtaining his or her consent, as that enables him or her to make informed decisions. The GDPR foresees specific information to provide to data subjects prior to obtaining consent. <i>In practice:</i> The following information should be provided for obtaining valid consent: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Controller's identity 2. Purpose of each processing operation 3. Type of data to be collected and use 4. Existence of the right to withdraw consent 5. Information about the use of the data for automated decision-making, where relevant 6. Possible risk of data transfers due to absence of appropriate safeguards.
'Unambiguous'	Consent must be given by a statement or a clear affirmative action, e.g. through a written or a recorded oral statement, including by electronic means. It must be obvious that the data subject has consented to the particular processing.

²⁹ In April 2018 WP29 issued the 'Guidelines on consent under Regulation 2016/679' and provided further guidance for the interpretation thereof; see WP29 Guidelines on Consent under Regulation 2016/679, WP259 rev.01, adopted on 28 November 2017, as last revised and adopted on 10 April 2018, p. 7 (hereinafter: WP29 Guidelines on Consent).

	<i>Example:</i> Pre-ticked boxes or opt-out constructions that require an intervention from the data subject to prevent agreement (e.g. ‘opt-out boxes’) may not entail the acquisition of an unambiguous consent.
‘Explicit’	For the processing of special categories of data (including data concerning health) consent must be provided explicitly.

The acquisition of consent per se is not a sufficient requirement to demonstrate compliance with legal requirements. Additionally, the GDPR foresees that the controller should be able to **demonstrate** that the data subject has consented to the processing of his or her personal data³⁰. More specifically, it is necessary that the controller not only acquires consent but also keeps track of it. Controllers are free to choose the preferred way to act so, as there are no predefined modalities for **keeping track of consent**.³¹ Finally, it is essential to remark that data subjects have the **right to withdraw consent** at any time. They should be entitled to do it without detriment, in an easy and swift way.

All the above mentioned requirements should be taken into account in the context of the Made4You project, and especially for the development/design of Careables.

2.4.2.2. *Legitimate interest*

Where personal data processing is necessary to pursue **legitimate interests** of a given organisation, those legitimate interests can serve as the legal ground for processing, provided that such interest are not overridden by the interests of fundamental rights and freedoms of the data subject. In other words, data protection legislation allows processing subject to a balancing test, which weighs the legitimate interests of the controller against the interests or fundamental rights of the data subjects. It does not exist an exhaustive list of all contexts or processing activities where the legitimate interest lawful basis can apply. However, the GDPR as well as WP29³² provided some guidance.

The examples are summarised below:

- Conventional direct marketing purposes and other forms of marketing or advertisement;
- processing to prevent fraud;
- employees’ monitoring for safety or management purposes;
- processing for physical security, IT and network security.

If a Made4You Consortium partner wishes to rely on the ‘legitimate interest’ for the processing of personal data, it should carry out a balancing test and thus demonstrate that the processing is necessary for the interests that wants to pursue. The test requires a context-specific risk-benefit assessment and implementation of potential mitigation measures. The legitimate interest will have to be lawful, sufficiently specific and not speculative.

³⁰ See WP29, Guidelines on consent under Regulation 2016/679, Adopted on 28 November 2017 as last revised and adopted on 10 April 2018, p. 20.

³¹ As WP29 pointed out, however, the processing of such information shall not lead to excessive amounts of additional data processing and controllers shall not process any more information than necessary for such aim.

³² See WP29, Opinion 06/2014 on the notion of legitimate interests of the data controller under Article 7 of Directive 95/46/EC, WP217, adopted on 9 April 2014.

2.4.3. Security of processing

The security of processing is a key element to be regarded for controllers as well as processors. This requirement is foreseen under Convention 108³³ and has been enshrined as a key data protection principle under the GDPR.³⁴

More specifically, according to Art. 32 GDPR, the controller is required to **implement technical and organisational measures** to ensure a level of security appropriate to the risk, taking into account the state of the art, the costs of implementation and the nature, scope, context and purposes of the processing as well as the risk for the rights and freedoms of individuals. GDPR provides a list of suggestions/examples for what kind of **security measures** might be considered 'appropriate to the risk'. These include³⁵:

- Pseudonymisation and encryption of personal data;
- Ensuring that the processing systems and services maintain confidentiality, integrity, availability and resilience;
- Ensuring the availability and access to personal data in a timely manner in the event of a physical or technical incident;
- A process for regular testing, assessing and evaluating the effectiveness of technical and organisational measures for ensuring the security of the processing.

The list provided by the GDPR is to be considered as non-exhaustive as it is up to the controller to identify the adequate measures to put in place to set an appropriate level of security of the processing, taking into account the state of the art and costs of implementation. The principle concerning the security of processing entails that the controller has to adopt a '**risk-based approach**'. Hence, in order to establish and implement the *appropriate technical and organisational measures*, the controller has to carry out a preliminary analysis to evaluate the risks to the rights and freedoms of the data subjects. When the processing of personal data is likely to result in a high risk, it is prescribed by law to carry out a **Data Protection Impact Assessment**. This process is essential for the controller to identify and minimise the data protection risks of a project (for a more detailed overview of DPIA requirements, see §2.5.4.4). Finally, it is to be mentioned as another duty for controllers under the principle of security of processing the requirement to notify any **breach of personal data** to the supervisory authority and in certain cases to the data subjects as well.

2.4.4. Accountability and promotion of compliance

This section outlines the key measures that controllers may put in place to facilitate compliance with data protection law.

2.4.4.1. Contractual agreements for the processing of personal data

The GDPR renewed the requirements concerning the role of data controllers and data processors and as well as their relationships with all the subjects involved in the processing of personal data.

- **Joint controllership**: the GDPR has formally regulated the hypothesis under which two or more controllers jointly determine the purposes and means of the processing (Art.

³³ Art. 7(1) Convention 108.

³⁴ See Art. 5(1)(f) GDPR and Art. 32 GDPR.

³⁵ See Art. 32(1) GDPR, lett. (a)- (e).

26 GDPR). In such occurrence, these subjects must be regarded as joint controllers. The main requirement for joint controllers is the regulation of responsibilities among themselves for the compliance with the Regulation. Such arrangement must be contractual. To this regard, controllers should sign a joint controllership agreement in order to regulate all aspects relevant under a data protection perspective and may consider to identify a point of contact for data subjects.

Controllers and Processors: as already required by DPD, whenever a controller uses a data processor an agreement must be in place. Data controllers must only appoint data processors who are able to provide sufficient guarantees that the requirements of the GDPR will be met and the rights of data subjects will be protected. According to Art. 28 GDPR, specific elements have to be included in a data controller/data processor agreement (e.g. the subject matter and the duration of the processing, the nature and purpose of the processing, the obligations and rights of the controller, etc.). Data processors must then act on the documented instructions of the controller.

- **Sub-processors:** also sub-processors must present sufficient guarantees for the compliance with GDPR. It is worth to be outlined that any sub-processor engaged by the data processor or by any other sub-processor must agree to process personal data exclusively only for the purposes to be carried out on behalf of the data controller and in accordance with his instructions, inasmuch as foreseen in a written (sub-processor) agreement.

For the purposes of Made4You, each Consortium partner must evaluate its role with respect to the processing activities it is undertaking. Once the role is identified, it will be necessary to conclude (where necessary) joint controllership agreements or data controller-data processor agreements.

2.4.4.2. Record of data processing activities

Another requirement set by the GDPR for the promotion of compliance concerns **the documentation and recording of processing activities**. Art. 30 GDPR requires that controllers must maintain a record of the processing activities carried out under their responsibility and to provide to the DPA when required. The information to be included are many (e.g. contact details of controller, joint controllers, DPO where applicable, the purposes of the processing, the description of the categories of data subjects, categories of recipients to whom personal data is disclosed, etc.). It is provided an exception not to keep records for organisations employing less than 250 persons. However, this not applies whether the organisation undertakes processing likely to result in a risk to the rights and freedoms of data subjects or the processing is not occasional or it includes special categories of personal data.

For the context of Made4You, this specific aspect is dealt under §2.5.4.1

2.4.4.3. Data Protection Impact Assessments

Under the DPD, controllers had the general obligation to notify the processing of personal data to the supervisory authority in order to be subject to their ‘preliminary check’. GDPR has alleviated the administrative burdens related to such requirement. Instead, data controllers must put in place proactive measures in order to demonstrate the compliance with the Reg-

ulation thus adopting a ‘risk-based approach’ in order to ensure that the processing is adequate to the risk. One of the means for controllers to demonstrate accountability and to adopt such a risk-based approach is the **Data Protection Impact Assessment**. According to WP29³⁶, DPIA is a “process designed to describe the processing, assess the necessity and proportionality of a processing and to help manage the risks to the rights and freedoms of natural persons resulting from the processing of personal data, by assessing them and determining the measures to address them”. The DPIA is a requirement set by Art. 35 GDPR and it is mandatory when a type of processing is ‘likely to result in a high risk’ to the rights and freedoms of natural persons. In this process, the controller must carry out an evaluation of the risks associated with a processing of personal data and define the measures needed to mitigate the envisaged risks.

Made4You Consortium partners have evaluated the opportunity to carry out DPIAs for the research project. Further information is provided in the Annex of this document.

2.4.5. Data Protection by Design

Another principle to take into account for the purposes of the Made4You Project is the principle of Privacy by Design, which has been recently codified under Article 25 of the GDPR:

“Taking into account the state of the art, the cost of implementation and the nature, scope, context and purposes of processing as well as the risks of varying likelihood and severity for rights and freedoms of natural persons posed by the processing, the controller shall, both at the time of the determination of the means for processing and at the time of the processing itself, implement appropriate technical and organisational measures, such as pseudonymisation, which are designed to implement data-protection principles, such as data minimisation, in an effective manner and to integrate the necessary safeguards into the processing in order to meet the requirements of this Regulation and protect the rights of data subjects”.

Such principle requires that privacy and data protection should be taken into account by stakeholders not only at the final stages of the product or service configuration, but from its very inception. In essence, data protection by design requires the integration of data protection into every processing activity and business practice.

Data protection by design may have a broad application. For example³⁷:

- For the developing new IT systems, services, products and processes that involve processing personal data;
- for the developing organisational policies, processes, business practices and/or strategies that have privacy implications;
- for physical design;
- for the use of personal data for new purposes.

Having such premised, it is essential that privacy and data protection are taken into account from the very outset of the project and Careables must be developed in application of these principles. The main recommendations and legal requirements for the development of the Careables platform are provided further below (§2.6).

³⁶ WP29, Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) and determining whether processing is “likely to result in a high risk” for the purposes of Regulation 2016/679, adopted on 4 April 2017 as last revised and adopted on 4 October 2017 (hereinafter: ‘Guidelines on DPIA’), p. 4.

³⁷ See ICO, Guide to the General Data Protection Regulation, section ‘Data protection by design and default’.

2.4.6. Rights of data subjects

To mitigate power imbalances between data subjects and controllers, data protection legislation establishes specific rights for data subjects, to let them exercise greater control over the processing of their personal data. To this regard, the controller is required to establish mechanisms aiming at facilitating the exercise of such rights by data subjects.

More specifically, the rights that data subjects are entitled to exercise are:

- **Right to information:** every data subject has the right to be informed about the collection and processing of his or her personal data. This requirement is a declination of the broader principle of transparency³⁸, which requires that any personal data processing should be generally be transparent to individuals. It should be transparent to individuals what data concerning them are collected, used, consulted or otherwise processed and to what extent will be processed.³⁹
- **Right to access:** individuals have the right to obtain, upon request, information about the processing of personal data relating to them, obtain a copy of such data as well as other supplementary information.
- **Right to rectification:** In application of the principle of accuracy – requiring that personal data shall be adequate and, where necessary, kept up to date – individuals have the right to have inaccurate personal data rectified.
- **Right to erasure:** occurring certain circumstances, individual have the right to have personal data erased (principle also commonly known as ‘the right to be forgotten’).
- **Right to restriction of processing:** occurring certain circumstances, data subjects have the right to temporarily restrict a controller from processing their personal data.
- **Right to data portability:** when the processing of personal data is grounded on specific lawful grounds (e.g. consent or a contract), data subjects are entitled to have their data transmitted directly from a controller to another, if technically possible. When applicable, this kind of right allows individuals to obtain and reuse their personal data across other services.
- **Right to object:** occurring certain circumstances, data subjects have the right to object the processing of their personal data.

Within the Made4You research project and the ‘Careables’ platform, data subjects should be enabled to exercise their rights in an easy and swift way, with particular regard to the Careables platform.

³⁸ Art. 5(1)(a) GDPR.

³⁹ Rec. 39 GDPR.

2.5 Key data protection legal requirements and recommendations for Made4You

2.5.1. Introduction

Made4You is a H2020 project whose scope it to create a central hub for citizens to share knowledge for the reproduction or self-creation of customised healthcare solutions. Its intention is to offer on a platform ('Careables') open documentation and instructions for the creation of healthcare solutions so that individuals are able to replicate solutions in any local lab or makerspace. As parallel and complementary action and as part of the work agreed under WP1,⁴⁰ Consortium partners have planned to carry out activities concerning the 'engagement and growth of the community'. Hence, the scope of WP1 is to promote the engagement of communities of different stakeholders⁴¹ by bringing them together and by connecting them in the field of open source healthcare solutions both on a local and global level.⁴² The identified objectives are:

- On a local level, part of Consortium partners have planned to function as 'primary hubs' for the connection of local communities of citizens, caregivers, healthcare professionals with the community of makers. This connection is organised through 'meet-ups' and 'Open days', where citizens and healthcare professionals, makers, designers and engineers gather together to evaluate and identify possibilities concerning the design and making of healthcare solutions.
- On a global level, Consortium partners target global networks of stakeholders and try to bring them together and to support the sharing of their knowledge and experiences through online collaborative tools, Careables and gatherings.

In the light of above, in order to achieve the results of the research project Consortium partners may carry out processing activities on individuals' personal data. Due to the topic of the research, data may include **data concerning health** of vulnerable data subjects (people with physical limitations and children) which may be collected for the co-design of personalized healthcare solutions. As preliminarily identified,⁴³ the following categories of data subjects represent the 'Target Groups' of individuals for Made4You:

- Adult patients
- Children with disabilities
- Parents/Legal guardians & Family members
- Healthcare professionals
- Caregivers
- Makers
- (Policy makers)

⁴⁰ WP1 – Engagement & Community Growth.

⁴¹ 'Stakeholders' are intended in the meaning outlines in the project GA, p.

⁴² WP1, Objectives.

⁴³ WP8, D8.1. – H Requirement No. 1, p. 6, Table 1: Made4You Target groups possibly involved in Made4You actions.

Finally, concerning the processing of data pertaining to such individuals, preliminary guidance has been already provided in WP8. Particular attentions has been put on:⁴⁴

- Consent as a component of Responsible Research and Innovation ('RRI');
- The specific procedures to obtain participants' consent based on Made4You specific data collection needs;
- The GDPR requirements for the acquisition of consent by data subjects;
- The templates for the acquisition of informed consent.

2.5.2. Participation of individuals within the Made4You Project

2.5.2.1. Consent of individuals as research participants

The ethics and legal requirements for the **acquisition of informed consent** by research participants have been summarised in WP8 ('D.8. H – Requirement No. 1'), where it has been established a process supporting the acquisition of consent of individuals (adults and minors) involved in Made4You activities. Hence, the **provision of information and the acquisition of consent** has to be regarded as a legal obligation as well as the expression of ethical principles to comply with for the purposes of the present research project.⁴⁵ In this context, Consortium partners have been provided with **informed consent templates**.⁴⁶ Every consent template required to be adapted with respect to the specific activities to carried by each stakeholder, the language in use, etc. The tailored approach for the process for obtaining individuals' consent has been illustrated in WP8 as follows:⁴⁷

Figure 1: Consent Process

It is worth to underline that the acquisition of individuals' consent for the participation in the research project must not be regarded as an alternative to the acquisition of consent of data

⁴⁴ Ivi, *passim*.

⁴⁵ EC, Options for strengthening responsible research and innovation. Report of the expert group on the state of the art in Europe on responsible research and innovation, 2013. See also, EC, Horizon 2020 Programme. Guidance. How to complete your ethics self-assessment, Version 6.0, 23 July 2018.

⁴⁶ See WP8, D8.1, p. 9.

⁴⁷ Ivi, p. 7, Figure 1: Consent obtaining process in Made4You.

subjects' for the processing of personal data. The first has been outlined in this Section – and further information can be retrieved in WP8, D8.1; the second is outlined below (§2.5.3.1), under the section 'Possible lawful grounds for the processing of personal data'.

2.5.3. Possible lawful grounds for the processing of personal data

Generally, the possible applicable legal basis that may be taken into consideration for processing activities carried out in the context of a research project are mainly:

- Consent (Art. 6(1)(a) GDPR);
- Necessity for legitimate interest of the controller or third party (Art. 6(1)(f) GDPR);

Concerning the processing of sensitive data, the possible legal grounds may be found in the following hypothesis.⁴⁸

- Explicit consent (Art. 9(2)(a) GDPR);
- Research purposes (Art. 9(2)(j) GDPR);
- Substantial public interest in the area of public health, such as “ensuring standards of quality and safety of health care and of medicinal products or medical devices, on the basis of Union or Member State law which provides suitable and specific measure to safeguard the fundamental rights and the interest of the data subject” (Art. 9(2)(i) GDPR).

For the purposes of Made4You, **consent** may represent one of the most appropriate lawful basis for the processing of personal data within Consortium partners' data processing activities. To this regard, a brief focus and recommendations are provided in the section below.

2.5.3.1. Consent of individuals as data subjects

Concerning the processing of personal data in the context of Made4You research project, Consortium partners may deem to rely on the lawful basis of **consent** (Art. 6(1)(a) GDPR) for the execution of their processing activities. Occurring such case, hereby are provided further recommendations, concerning in particular the acquisition and management of consent for the processing of personal data.

1. Ensure that consent is always acquired in a lawful way: Each Consortium partner must ensure that the acquisition of consent occurs always in compliance with the criteria listed under section §2.4.2.1. Namely, consent must be: freely given, specific, informed, unambiguous, and explicit.

For instance:

- Consent should be acquired as a result of an unambiguous action by the data subject, and where sensitive data are processed, it must be explicit. Therefore, Consortium partners processing personal (and sensitive) data should adopt and make use of forms for acquisition of informed consent forms with individuals involved in the research project.

⁴⁸ See also WP29, Guidelines on consent, Section 7.2.

- Consent must be ‘informed’. When acquiring consent, Consortium partners should ensure that relevant information is always provided concerning the processing activity.

Moreover, as WP29 puts it⁴⁹, when consent is a legal basis for conducting research in accordance with the GDPR, consent for the use of personal data should be distinguished from other consent requirements that serve as an ethical standard or procedural obligation.⁵⁰

2. **Consent management:** demonstration of consent acquisition is a key legal requirement under data protection law. It is important that consent giving is backed up by a clear audit trail of consent. For instance:
 - Consortium partners should securely store (electronically or on paper) information sheets and consent forms provided by participants.
3. **Ensure that data subjects can withdraw consent:** Consortium partners must ensure that consent can be as easily withdrawn as it has been provided. Not meeting this requirement may affect the validity of consent.

2.5.4. Further technical and organisational measures

This section reports on the **technical and organisational measures** that Consortium partners may evaluate to adopt in the context of Made4You project. This outline is intended to provide soft guidance to Consortium partners, whose compliance with any legal requirement foreseen by law has to be attributed to their sole responsibility.

2.5.4.1. Record of Processing Activities

In line with Article 30 of the GDPR, Consortium partners are required to keep written records of all processing activities involving personal data undertaken during the execution of the research project. In order to facilitate the meeting of documentation requirements foreseen by GDPR, Consortium partners may evaluate the adoption of templates provided by national DPAs.⁵¹ The relevant information to be contained in such document is foreseen under Art. 30 GDPR. Generally, the following information concerning processing activities should be reported:

- Name and contact details of the organisation (and where applicable, other controllers and DPO);
- The purposes of the processing;
- A description of the categories of individuals and categories of personal data;
- Categories of recipients of personal data;
- Details of transfers to third countries including documenting the transfer mechanism safeguards in place;
- Retention periods for the storage of personal data;
- A description of technical and organisational security measures.

⁴⁹ Ibidem.

⁵⁰ Ivi, p. 28.

⁵¹ Many templates drafted by National DPAs are retrievable on the Internet. E.g. UK DPA’s (ICO), Italian DPA’s (Garante per la Protezione dei Dati Personali), French DPA’s (CNIL) etc.

The drafting of records of processing activities may be also useful in order to identify the data processor(s) and sub-processor(s), with whom it will be necessary to sign a Data Processing Agreement to set the key obligations between parties with respect to the processing of personal data, as foreseen by art. 28 GDPR.

2.5.4.2. Security of processing

Consortium partners should also analyse and evaluate the **technical and organisational measures to ensure that the processing of personal data is adequate to the risk**, as required by art. 32 GDPR. This legal requirement implies that controllers/Consortium partners should consider for instance to carry out risk analysis, to draft organisational policies, and to implement physical and technical measures for data security. The GDPR does not contain an exhaustive list of security measures that organisations should have in place. The GDPR requires to have a level of security that is ‘appropriate’ to the risks presented by the processing, and therefore the controller has to evaluate such risks in relation to the state of the art and costs of implementation, as well as the nature, scope, context and purpose of the processing.

This approach has to be regarded as the substantiation of the GDPR’s risk-based approach, for which there is no ‘one size fits all’ solution to information security. What may be ‘appropriate’ for a certain organisation may not be appropriate for another, depending on circumstances, processing activities, and risks. Before deciding the appropriate measures, organisations are required to assess their information risk by taking into account for instance the following factors:

- the nature and extent of the organisation’s premises and computer systems;
- the number of staff the extent of their access to personal data;
- the existence of data processor, carrying out processing activities on behalf of the controller.

Where appropriate, controllers should look to use measures such as **pseudonymisation and encryption**. This is of particular importance for the purposes of Made4You project, given the sensitive nature of the processed data.

The measures chosen by each controller must then ensure the ‘confidentiality, integrity and availability’ of systems and services and of the personal data that are processed. The measures must also enable to restore access and availability to personal data in a timely manner in the event of a physical or technical incident. Controllers may also evaluate to put in place appropriate processes to test the effectiveness of the taken measures that may be necessary to undertake for any required improvements.

2.5.4.3. Data minimisation and data retention

In application of the key principle of data minimisation foreseen under Art. 5(1)(c) GDPR, Consortium partners must evaluate processes and procedures for ensuring that the processing of personal data is adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary for the identified purposes. Consortium partners may also assess whether the purposes could be achieved with either less data or with properly anonymised datasets.

Particularly, Consortium partners may consider to define the period of retention of personal data and to adopt a **data retention policy**. Also, when the period of retention is identified, Consortium partners should evaluate the appropriate actions to take with regards to anonymising or erasing the data that have been processed.

2.5.4.4. Data Protection Impact Assessments

One of the main innovations of the GDPR has been the formal provision by law of the concept of a **Data Protection Impact Assessment**. The DPIA is a process designed to describe the processing, assess its necessity and proportionality and help manage the risks to the rights and freedoms of natural persons resulting from the processing of personal data by assessing them and determining the measures to address them. This legal requirement is foreseen under art. 35 GDPR and has been further subject to the interpretative guidance provided by WP29.⁵² The DPIA is an important element of accountability and, not less significantly, a tool for building and demonstrating compliance. Herein below is provided an explanatory table concerning the DPIA requirement.

Table 4: DPIA requirements

When is it necessary to carry out a DPIA?	<p>The DPIA has to be conducted when the processing of personal data is “likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons” (Art. 35 GDPR).</p> <p>According to WP29⁵³, a processing is likely to result in a high risk – inter alia – if:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data of vulnerable data subjects (e.g. people having health care needs, minors, patients, elderly, etc.) are processed; - Sensitive data (e.g. data concerning health) are processed.
	The DPIA should be conducted prior to the processing.
Why is it necessary?	<p>The execution of the DPIA is a requirement, foreseen under Art. 35 GDPR.</p> <p>Non-compliance with DPIA requirements can lead to fines imposed by the competent Authority.</p>
Who has to do it?	The DPIA has to be carried out by the data controller (i.e. the entity/organisation that determines the purposes and means of the processing (Art. 4(7) GDPR)).
How to do it?	The frameworks/methodologies that can be adopted by controllers are many. The GDPR specifies general criteria but does not specify nor require to adopt specific framework/methodologies.

In the context of Made4You project, Consortium partners have evaluated the opportunity to carry out Data Protection Impact Assessments for the project. A brief overview thereof as well as the adopted Methodology is provided in the Annex to this document.

2.5.4.5. Data breach

A **personal data breach** is a breach of security that leads to the accidental or unlawful destruction, loss, alteration, unauthorised disclosure of, or access to, personal data. A personal data breach can be broadly defined as a security incident that has affected the confidentiality,

⁵² WP29, Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) and determining whether processing is “likely to result in a high risk” for the purposes of Regulation 2016/679, WP248 rev.01, adopted on 4 April 2017 as last revised and adopted on 4 October 2017.

⁵³ Ibid.

integrity or availability of personal data. In short, there exist be a personal data breach whenever any personal data is lost, destroyed, corrupted or disclosed; if someone accesses the data or passes it on without proper authorisation; or if the data is made unavailable, for example, when it has been encrypted by ransomware, or accidentally lost or destroyed.⁵⁴ According to Arts. 33-34 GDPR, in the case of a personal data breach, the controller shall without undue delay, and where feasible, not later than 72 hours after having become aware of it, notify the personal data breach to the supervisory competent authority – unless the personal data breach is unlikely to result in a risk to the rights and freedom of natural persons. Also, in certain circumstances, a personal data breach has to be communicated to the data subject. In order to comply with such requirement, Consortium partners may wish to ensure to have robust **breach detection, investigation and internal reporting policies and procedures in place**, also in order to facilitate decision-making about notification and communication to the relevant supervisory authority and the affected individuals. Also, in case a data breach will occur, controllers have to **keep a record** of it, regardless of whether the requirement of notification exists.

2.6 Key data protection legal requirements and recommendations for Careables platform

2.6.1. Introduction

This section aims at outlining the key legal requirements that are applicable to Made4You and that may have an impact for the development of the Careables platform. One of the most important elements that have to be taken into account for such development is the principle of data protection by design, which is outlined in §2.6.2. §2.6.3 concerns the topic of the handling of personal information in the platform, whereas §2.6.4 is focused on the role of consent in Careables. Further observations are then provided concerning information duties (§2.6.5) and data subjects rights (§2.6.2). A final section (§2.6.7) summarises further technical measures that may be relevant for Careables.

2.6.2. The principle of data protection by design

In past, privacy and data protection were perceived by organisations only as issues related to legal compliance, a formal process limited to the mere drafting of privacy policies and further documentation of legal nature. A notable gap existed between formal legal principles and the possibility to translate them into actionable legal requirements. As of the 1970s, it started to spread a different idea contrasting with this background, aiming at demonstrating that privacy concerns may not be increased but on the contrary addressed throughout the development of technologies. Later on, the term “privacy by design” was used by Anne Cavoukian⁵⁵, at the time Information and Privacy Commissioner of Ontario. The concept was described as a sum of ‘7 foundational principles’⁵⁶, emphasizing the importance of proactivity in taking

⁵⁴ See ICO, Guide to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), Section ‘Personal data breaches’.

⁵⁵ A. Cavoukian, Privacy by design: the 7 foundational principles, Information and privacy commissioner of Ontario, 2009.

⁵⁶ The “seven foundational principles” are: 1. Proactive not Reactive, Preventative not Remedial; 2. Privacy as the Default Setting; Privacy Embedded into Design; 4. Full Functionality — Positive-Sum, not Zero-Sum; 5. End-

into account privacy requirements as of the design phase and throughout the entire lifecycle of data.

After several years, in 2016 the **General Data Protection Regulation formalised the principle of ‘data protection by design’ and enshrined it into European law**. Now, it represents a legal requirement⁵⁷ which provides the controller to implement “appropriate technical and organisational measures” at the design phase as well as the operation phase of a given technology, for embedding data protection safeguards in an effective way into technologies. The principle is related to the principle of accountability, set out under art. 5(2) GDPR and further expanded by art. 24 GDPR, which determines the controller’s responsibility to comply and demonstrate compliance with the law as well as to adopt a risk-based approach for the determination measures to necessary to be implemented for the processing, as adequate.

Under a less abstract point of view, the concept of data protection by design implies the integration of privacy/data protection requirements in the engineering of products and services. **Having such premised, it is implied that the principle of data protection by design must be embedded in the technology of Careables from the early phases of its development.**

2.6.2.1. The various dimension of the obligation of data protection by design

The concept of data protection by design has been recently the subject of a guidance document provided by the European Data Protection Board (EDPB).⁵⁸ According to EDPB, the obligation of data protection by design has various dimensions.

1. Firstly, data protection by design requires that the processing of personal data should always be the **outcome of a design project**. Safeguards have to be considered both at the design and at the operational phase of the project concerned. **Project requirements have to identify the protection of individuals and their personal data.**
2. The second dimension concerns the **risk management approach**. The selected measures for the protection of personal data must be the outcome of the evaluation of the risk that may concern individuals. Organisation shall choose safeguards among the ones that are available by taking, amongst other, into consideration the state of art and the costs of implementation of measures.
3. **Measures must be appropriate and effective**. Such measures are considered as effective when they ensure and are able to demonstrate compliance with data protection legislation, and they are adequate to protect the rights of individuals whose data are processed.
4. The **safeguards** that have been identified should be **integrated into the processing**.

The mentioned dimensions of data protection by design are of equal importance and represent an integral part of the accountability principle.

to-End Security — Full Lifecycle Protection; 6. Visibility and Transparency — Keep it Open; 7. Respect for User Privacy — Keep it User-Centric.

⁵⁷ Art. 25 GDPR.

⁵⁸ See EDPS, Opinion 5/2018, Preliminary Opinion on privacy by design, 31 May 2018 (hereinafter: ‘EDPS Opinion on privacy by design’).

2.6.2.2. The operationalisation of data protection by design

The principle of data protection by design can be further **operationalised**. Namely, it may be translated into practice through:

1. The definition of a **methodology** to integrate the privacy and data protection requirements;
2. **Identification and implementation of adequate technical and organisational measures** to be integrated into the processes, procedures and systems;
3. The integration of the **support for privacy in the management and governance** of the project, by defining tasks, resources and responsibilities.

The methodologies that may be taken into account for the operationalisation of data protection by design are many. A relevant example may be retrieved on the methodology issued by the PRIPARE research project.⁵⁹ As described by the EDPS in its Opinion on data protection by design, the PRIPARE proposed Methodology⁶⁰ constitutes an example of methodology focused on the whole project lifecycle as it proposes comprehensive privacy related actions and deliverables along different project phases. More in detail, the PRIPARE project proposes a project structure in seven different phases which have the aim to match the classic system engineering phases and to merge these with the most prevalent engineering practices (e.g. ISO 15288⁶¹). The seven phases as identified are: 1. Analysis, 2. Design, 3. Implementation, 4. Verification, 5. Release, 6. Maintenance, 7. Decommission.

The approach suggested in PRIPARE is scalable and may be adapted to the single circumstances of the project and the stakeholders within a given project. For the purposes of the Made4You project it may be taken into account the PRIPARE 'lightweight' approach, as below reported and outlined.

Figure 2: PRIPARE's lightweight itinerary

⁵⁹ Preparing Industry to Privacy-by-design by supporting its Application in Research (PRIPARE), H2020 programme, Grant agreement no 610613. See also EDPS Opinion on privacy by design, p. 15.

⁶⁰ PRIPARE, Privacy- and Security-by-Design Methodology Handbook, V1.00, 31 December 2015 (hereinafter: 'PRIPARE Methodology Handbook').

⁶¹ ISO/IEC 15288:2015 Systems and software engineering -- System life cycle processes.

The 'lightweight approach' is suggested for small organisations and may be a key starting point for Made4You and *inter alia* for the development of the Careables platform. Accordingly, the process of development of the Careables platform may be based on the following different phases:

- Promotion and Awareness
- Analysis
- Design
- Implementation
- Release and Maintenance

The following sections will further outline these project phases, having regard to shape the PRIPARE proposed approach according to the context and consequent specificities of the Made4You project.

Phase 0: Promotion and Awareness

This first phase 'Promotion and Awareness' concerns the environment and infrastructure of a given organisation. For large organisations, this is translated in an internal privacy architecture to support its policy objectives, including an internal organisational structure and governance model. In the context of smaller organisations, a certain degree of adaptation is needed. To this extent, it is suggested the **promotion of privacy and data protection awareness** towards the components of small organisations. It is also recommended the establishment of **informal privacy information repositories** with links to available material on the subject which may be consulted when necessary.⁶²

Output:

The promotion of data protection and privacy awareness should be enacted and maintained on a continuous basis through:

1. Matter specific trainings (privacy and data protection) for organisations' staff;
2. Provision of accessible informational documentation to the involved staff.

→ In the context of Made4You, privacy and data protection awareness is promoted as of the early stages of the project and maintained under a continuous basis, under the lead of WP6.⁶³

→ Informational documentation has been as will be further on provided (e.g. see as output of tasks foreseen under WP8 – 'Ethics requirements' and WP6 – 'Legal & Ethical Aspects').

Phase 1: Analysis

The execution of a project entailing the processing of personal data requires beforehand the identification of the applicable legal requirements and the adoption of a risk-based approach. The aim is to scope and fully understand the environment on which the project objective will be operated. The Analysis phase may be further divided into three main steps.

⁶² PRIPARE Methodology Handbook, p. 22.

⁶³ Further information may be retrieved in Made4You Grant Agreement, p. 85.

1. A first step entails the identification of the **framework** in a **legal analysis**, providing the key definitions of data protection law, the functional description of the project, the inventory of the **applicable principles and legal requirements**.
2. The second step concerns the **operationalisation** of the identified legal requirements under the first phase for embedding of such principles into the specific tasks of the project. The process of operationalisation of data protection and privacy principles implies the gradual and granular transposition of privacy principles in guidelines, the guidelines in criteria, and criteria on requirements to be followed in the design of the project objective.
3. The third step concerns the adoption of a **risk-based approach** and entails the execution of a preliminary **Data Protection Impact Assessment** to evaluate of the risks that may result to the rights and freedoms of natural persons.

Output:

- Analysis of the legal framework and the applicable principles and guidelines;
- Operationalisation of principles and guidelines in requirements;
- Execution of a Preliminary Data Protection Impact Assessment.

- ➔ For Made4You Project, the analysis of the legal framework and applicable principles and guidelines is carried out in the present Deliverable. An overview of applicable principles and guidelines is provided in the Annex;
- ➔ The operationalisation of principles and guidelines in requirements will be carried out in D6.2 – ‘Implementation of the legal and ethical requirements’.
- ➔ The execution of preliminary Data Protection Impact Assessments has been done. Further information is provided in the Annex of this document.

Phase 2: Design

While the Analysis phase focuses on *what* has to be developed, the Design phase focuses on *how* it has to be done. Having the list of privacy controls, the relevant key persons involved in the architecture design of the project may rely on the relevant information and criteria to take into account for the execution of the project.

Output:

- Key persons involved in the project may identify and set the right architecture for implementation, on the basis on the principles, guidelines and requirements provided.

- ➔ The process of architecture design within the task concerning the platform and tools development (T3.4 – ‘Iterative online platform and tools development’, due by M36) must comply with the principles, guidelines and requirements outlined in the context of the Project.

Phase 3: Implementation

The Implementation phase aims at ensuring that developers will follow the best security and privacy practices that are relevant for the underlying system.

→ The process of implementation within the task concerning the platform and tools development (T3.4 – ‘Iterative online platform and tools development’, due by M36) must comply with the principles, guidelines and requirements outlined in the context of the Project.

Phase 4: Release

The Release phase includes the process that may be followed immediately before or in the moment of a release of a system. This phase may include the following sub-steps:

- **Creation of a system decommissioning policy/plan:** it is recommended to adopt a decommissioning plan to guide system operator whenever the system ceases its operation;
- **A final data protection and privacy review:** any project with potential privacy and security issues should be thoroughly evaluated to ensure its compliance with data protection legislation requirements;
- **Publication of the DPIA report:** in order to demonstrate accountability and transparency towards individuals and data subjects, the publication of the DPIA report, a summary of the same or its conclusions may represent a good practice.⁶⁴

Outputs:

- System decommissioning plan/policy;
- Final data protection and privacy review;
- Publication of a DPIA report/summary/conclusions.

In the context of the Made4You:

- It is recommended the drafting of a system decommissioning policy/plan to guide the system operator occurring the case in which the system will not be operative anymore;
- It is planned to be provided a final data protection and privacy review (D6.3 – ‘Validation and policy recommendations’).
- It may be evaluated to proceed to the publication of the DPIA concerning the development of the platform.

2.6.3. The handling of personal data within Careables

The principles of data protection have been outlined under §2.4.1 apply as well for the development of the platform. In the context of the development of Careables, Consortium partners which will act as data controllers must ensure that the processing respect all such principles. **Lawfulness, fairness and transparency:** all processing operations must be based on lawful grounds (e.g. consent or legitimate interests).

Purpose limitation: before the collection of personal data, controllers must define the purposes of the processing operations.

⁶⁴ WP29 ‘Guidelines on DPIA’, p. 18.

Data minimisation: once the purposes of data processing are defined, controllers have to determine the types of personal data which are necessary to process to achieve the identified purposes.

Accuracy: controllers must put in place appropriate processes to ensure the accuracy of personal data, to record the source thereof and provide data subjects the possibility to rectify their data.

Storage limitation: personal data must not be stored for longer than is necessary for the defined processing purposes. Controllers are required to identify a period of retention of personal data and after its expiration they must either delete or anonymise the processed personal data.

Security measures: appropriate security measures must be implemented. The appropriateness of such measures are decided on the basis of the personal data concerned and risk associated with each processing activity.

Accountability: during the development of the Careables platform and in accordance with the accountability principle, Consortium partners are required to ensure and demonstrate compliance with the GDPR.

2.6.4. The role of consent within the Careables scenario

In the context of the Made4You project, the processing of personal data within the Careables platform will have to be grounded on one or more **lawfulness grounds** (see above § 2.4).

Having regard to the environment of the Careables platform, the applicable lawfulness ground to take into consideration may be primarily regard to data subject's **consent**.

2.6.4.1. Key elements for the general acquisition of consent on Careables

Within the Careables platform, the main implications to be taken into account concerning the legal requirement of consent may be summarised as follows:

1. **Ensure that consent is acquired lawfully:** on Careables, the acquisition of consent should occur in compliance with the criteria listed in the section above (viz. Freely given, freely given, specific, informed, unambiguous, and where applicable, explicit).

For instance:

- For each purposes of the data processing, data subjects should be in the position to choose freely for what purpose he or she wants to consent;
- A unique consent form for more purposes should be avoided;
- Consent requests must be separate from other website terms and conditions;
- Avoid the use pre-ticked boxes or any other method of default consent;
- Provide information about the processing with all elements foreseen by law and use a clear and plain language.

2. **Consent management:** it is important to evaluate and adopt a mechanisms for demonstrating that data subjects have provided consent. For instance, Careables platform should allow to:

- keep a record of when and how it has been obtained the consent from individuals;
- retain information on the session in which consent was expressed;

- keep a record of exactly what kind of information was provided to individuals;
 - document of consent workflow at the time made by individuals.
3. **Ensure that data subjects can withdraw consent:** it shall be ensured that consent may be as easily withdrawn as it was provided. Not meeting this requirement may affect the validity of consent.

2.6.4.2. Further specifications/best practices concerning cookies

On the basis of the guidance provided by WP29, this section outlines the main legal requirements⁶⁵ to be taken into account on Careables whether it is intended to make use of **cookies** or similar **tracking technologies**.

- ✓ **Specific information:** an immediately visible notice (e.g. a banner) that various types of cookies are being used by the website should be provided. Such notice may give information according to a layered approach – for instance, providing a link where users can find out more about types of cookies/tracking technologies being used. Information should be clear and easily comprehensible. Information such as retention period of cookies, details of third party cookies and other technical information should also be included.
- ✓ **Prior consent:** it should be provided an immediately visible notice where users may agree to cookies being set by the websites. This because as of principle, consent typically has to be given before the processing to be started.
- ✓ **Indication of wishes expressed by users' active behaviour:** there should be given information as to how the users can express and later withdraw their wishes concerning cookies including information on the action required to express such a preference.
- ✓ **Ability to choose freely:** it should be foreseen a mechanism by which the user can choose to accept all or some or decline cookies as well as an option for the user to subsequently change a prior preference regarding cookies.

2.6.5. Provision of information to data subjects

The GDPR underlines the importance of transparency. Data subjects have to be properly informed on the processing activities concerning them. Within Careables, it is important that the relevant information concerning the processing activities is provided to data subjects. According to Arts. 13-14 GDPR, specific information must be disclosed to data subjects. Herein below is provided a recapitulative table of information to be provided:⁶⁶

- The name and contact details of the controller;
- The purposes of the processing;
- The lawful basis for the processing;
- The categories of personal data;

⁶⁵ See WP29, Working Document on obtaining consent for cookies, p. 2.

⁶⁶ See also ICO, Guide to the General Data Protection Regulation, Section 'Individual Rights'.

- The recipients or categories of recipients of the personal data;
- The details of transfers of the personal data to any third countries or international organisations;
- The retention periods for the personal data;
- The rights available to individuals in respect of the processing;
- The right to withdraw consent;
- The right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority;
- The source of the personal data;
- The details of whether individuals are under a statutory or contractual obligation to provide the personal data;
- The details of the existence of automated decision-making, including profiling.

It is therefore important that within the Careables platform there will be a dedicated (and easily retrievable) place where information over the processing of personal data is provided.

2.6.6. Effectiveness of the exercise of data subjects' rights

GDPR gives data subjects a comprehensive list of rights to grant them more control over their personal data. To enable data subjects to effectively exercise their rights, the controllers must evaluate and put in place **organisational and technical measures in order to let data subjects exercise of rights** is an easy way.

An exemplificative list of technical and organizational measures – subject to partners' further evaluation – is provided below:

- **Organizational Measures**
 - o Information concerning the possibility to exercise their rights must be provided to data subjects;
 - o Partners may evaluate to identify a single point of contact in the case data subjects wish to exercise their rights;
 - o Partners may also evaluate the opportunity to establish a policy concerning the modalities, timing, circumstances occurring the case a data subjects' right wish to exercise his or her rights.
- **Technical measures:** partners should also implement technical means enabling them to accommodate data subject's requests. For instance:
 - o **Withdrawing consent:** if a data subject wishes to withdraw his or her consent, there should be a technical means enabling it to identify the data belonging to that particular individual, erase/anonymise it and ensure that his or her data are no longer processed during the project.
 - o **Right to access:** Consortium partners may evaluate to put in place tools or means enabling the extraction of personal data relating for to an individual and provide a copy of such data.
 - o **Right to erasure:** partners must have the means to ensure erasure of personal data.

The examples provided above are only intended to give a brief overview of the opportunities that Consortium partners may take into account during the design and development of the platform. Further guidance is intended also to be provided in D6.2.

2.6.7. Further technical and organisational measures

2.6.7.1. Security of processing

Ensuring that data processed by Careables are kept secure is an important element for the platform. As already outlined above (§2.5.4.2), also for the development of the Careables platform Consortium partners should also analyse and evaluate the **technical and organisational measures to ensure that the processing of personal data is adequate to the risk**, as required by art. 32 GDPR.

2.6.7.2. Data Protection Impact Assessment for Careables

In order to provide a level of security appropriate to the risks of processing, it has been conducted a prior **data protection impact assessment for the development of the Careables platform**. A brief recapitulative of the Careables DPIA may be found as annexed in the document.

2.6.7.3. Data breach

In order to comply with such requirement, it is important that also for Careables are present tools, policies and procedures for **breach detection investigation and internal reporting**. Also, as already outlined above (§2.5.4.5) in case a data breach will occur to the platform, it is essential to **keep a record** of it, regardless of whether exists the requirement of notification to the DPA and data subjects.

3 IPRs framework

3.1 Introduction

Legal issues that may arise while developing Careables (= open healthcare solutions shared on the careables platform) also concern two sets of intellectual property rights, namely copyright and patents. Hence, this section starts with describing the EU and international legislation regulating copyright under which an author enjoys exclusive economic rights with regards to his or her artistic/literary works. Since the aim of Made4You Consortium is to encourage publication and promotion of Careables that are designed as open as possible (to allow as many people as possible to use them without particular limitations), the analysis goes further to examine the applicability of open source software licenses (hereinafter: OSS or OSSL) and Creative Commons licenses (hereinafter: CCL or CC). Their common ground is a certain level of freedom to use, with regards to otherwise copyrighted work, given by the licensor (the author) to licensees (the public). Upon a common agreement with the Consortium partners, there may be Careables enjoying a patent protection. If products enjoying a patent protection as a whole or only with regard to some components are to be considered careables, this section also provides an overview of the international patent law and examines its alternative – the open source hardware license (hereinafter: OSHL or OSH), whose idea behind and aim do not differ significantly from the goals of OSSL and CCL.

3.2 Copyright

3.2.1. About the copyright protection in general

Copyright (or author's right) is a term used to describe "the rights that creators have over their literary and artistic works"⁶⁷. Usually, the author of the work will enjoy the copyright protection if he/she is the national of one of the countries belonging to the Berne Union (in total, 176 contracting parties; including all EU Member States⁶⁸) whether or not the work has been published. Moreover, authors who are not nationals of the Berne Union but their work has been published for the first time in one of the countries of the Union or simultaneously published in the country of the Union as well as the third country⁶⁹ enjoy the same protection as described before. International, EU and national legislations do not provide an exhaustive list of works that are usually covered by copyright protection. However, broadly speaking, commonly protected under copyright throughout the world are works belonging to *literary and artistic works*. This term includes every production in the literary, **scientific** and artistic domain including, but not limited to books, pamphlets and other writings; lectures, addresses, sermons and other works of the same nature; dramatic or dramatic-musical works; choreographic works and entertainments in dumb show; musical compositions with or without words; cinematographic works to which are assimilated works expressed by a process analogous to cinematography; works of drawing, painting, architecture, sculpture, engraving and lithography; photographic works to which are assimilated works expressed by a process analogous to photography; works of applied art; illustrations, maps, plans, sketches and three-dimensional works relative to geography, topography, architecture or science⁷⁰; computer programs, databases. Importantly, copyright protection extends only to **expressions of works**, and not to ideas, procedures, methods of operations or mathematical concepts as such. Authors enjoy two types of **exclusive rights**, namely economic and moral rights. **Economic rights** allow an author to derive financial reward from the use of her work by others and to prevent certain uses in relation to such work. Thus, the author can prohibit or authorize: its *reproduction* in various forms, such as printed publication or sound recording; its *public performance*, such as in a play or musical work; its *recording*, for example, in the form of compact discs or DVDs; its *broadcasting*, by radio, cable or satellite; its *translation* into other languages; and its *adaptation*, such as a novel into a film screenplay. On the other hand, **moral rights** protect the non-economic interests of the author. They include the *right to claim authorship* of a work and the *right to oppose changes* to a work that could harm the creator's reputation. Finally, the enjoyment and the exercise of both economic and moral rights **shall not be subject to any formality**. In other words, this means that an author in the EU will enjoy all the rights given under the copyright protection of his/her work from the moment such work has been created. Under the Berne Convention for the Protection of Literary and Artistic Works (hereinafter: the Berne Convention), exclusive rights afforded by copyright protection

⁶⁷ <http://www.wipo.int/copyright/en/>.

⁶⁸ For the full list, see http://www.wipo.int/treaties/en/ShowResults.jsp?lang=en&treaty_id=15.

⁶⁹ Article 3, Berne Convention for the Protection of Literary and Artistic Works (as amended on September 28, 1979), available at: http://www.wipo.int/wipolex/en/treaties/text.jsp?file_id=283693.

⁷⁰ Article 2, Berne Convention for the Protection of Literary and Artistic Works (as amended on September 28, 1979), available at: http://www.wipo.int/wipolex/en/treaties/text.jsp?file_id=283693.

should last for the lifetime of the author and fifty years after his or her death.⁷¹ In Europe, under the Directive 2006/116/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2006 on the term of protection of copyright and certain related rights (hereinafter: the ‘Term Directive’), the protection of the copyrighted work lasts for 70 years after the death of the author.⁷² Under the principle of exhaustion of intellectual property rights the copyright owner loses the right to control, for instance, of a resale of the work once it has been placed on the relevant market either by himself or with his consent.⁷³ The exhaustion system may be of international, national or regional nature. For the relevance of the Made4You project is the regional exhaustion system as it is the one that is followed by the European Union. Under such system, the sale of a work in one of the Member States party to the trade/custom union agreement exhausts the right to resell in the others. This approach has been supported by the Court of Justice of the European Union by stating that “once goods [...] have been placed on the market of one country within the EU by or with the consent of the owner of the rights in that country, the right holder cannot prevent the subsequent export/import and resale of such goods in other parts of the EU under parallel intellectual property rights (parallel import)”.⁷⁴ On the other hand, placing on market does not include activities that can be indefinitely repeated and can result in an infinite number of users of the protected work since those rights are considered, by the EU law, as made available to the public and therefore in ‘performance of services’. As a consequence, the principle of the exhaustion of rights does not apply to such activities.⁷⁵

3.2.2. Overview of the EU Copyright Framework

3.2.2.1. Introduction

Currently, there are 10 applicable Directives dealing with copyright within the EU, namely: the Software Directive⁷⁶, the Rental and Lending Rights Directive⁷⁷, the Satellite and Cable

⁷¹ Article 7, Berne Convention for the Protection of Literary and Artistic Works (as amended on September 28, 1979), available at: http://www.wipo.int/wipolex/en/treaties/text.jsp?file_id=283693.

⁷² Tryggvadottir R, *European Libraries and the Internet: Copyright and Extended Collective Licenses*, KU Leuven Centre for IT&IP Law Series, 2018, p. 17, and Article 1 of the Directive 2006/116/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2006 on the term of protection of copyright and certain related rights (codified version), available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX%3A32006L0116>.

⁷³ Ubertazzi B, *The Principle of Free Movement of Goods: Community Exhaustion and parallel imports*, p. 38. In: Stamataoudi I, Torremans P, *EU Copyright Law: A Commentary*, Elgar Commentaries 2014.

⁷⁴ Ubertazzi B, *The Principle of Free Movement of Goods: Community Exhaustion and parallel imports*, p. 40. In: Stamataoudi I, Torremans P, *EU Copyright Law: A Commentary*, Elgar Commentaries 2014.

⁷⁵ *Ibid*, p. 43.

⁷⁶ Directive 2009/24/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 April 2009 on the legal protection of computer programs (Codified version) (Text with EEA relevance).

⁷⁷ Directive 2006/115/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2006 on rental right and lending right and on certain rights related to copyright in the field of intellectual property (codified version).

Directive⁷⁸, **the Term Directive**⁷⁹, the Database Directive⁸⁰, the Resale Right Directive⁸¹, **the Information Society Directive**⁸², the Enforcement Directive⁸³, the Orphan Works Directive⁸⁴, and the Collective Rights Management Directive⁸⁵. This deliverable will address only those Directives that are of the direct concern for the Made4You project (highlighted in bold).

For the sake of completeness and clarification, *directive* is a legislative act that sets out a goal that all EU countries must achieve. However, it is up to the individual countries to devise their own laws on how to reach these goals. This means that a directive is applicable to all EU Member States, it sets certain aims and requirements that have to be achieved in each Member State, it sets a process for it to be implemented, and national authorities have to adapt or create a legislation in order to meet the goals of the directive concerned. On the other side, there are regulations. *Regulation* is a binding legislative act. It must be applied in its entirety across the EU.

The EU copyright law is mainly regulated with the directives which implies that national laws of Member States may still apply, and consequently, differ in certain instances. This further means that different rules with regard to copyright protection, exclusive rights and exceptions may still apply to makers publishing their documentation onto the Careables platform (depending on the Member State of their residence / main establishment). Hence, authors should be advised always to check their national copyright legislation as a first step and then, as a second step, to make a decision about licensing their works.

3.2.2.2. Directive 2001/29/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 May 2001 on the harmonisation of certain aspects of copyright and related rights in the information society (hereinafter: the 'ISD')

3.2.2.2.1. Exclusive **economic** rights of authors

In the first place, the ISD does not define the notion of 'authors'. Hence, anyone who is considered an author by the national law of the Member State in question will be covered by the Directive. The ISD concerns the legal protection of copyright in the framework of the internal market of the European Union and it entitles Member States to prescribe within its national legislation several exclusive rights of the authors.

⁷⁸ Council Directive 93/83/EEC of 27 September 1993 on the coordination of certain rules concerning copyright and rights related to copyright applicable to satellite broadcasting and cable retransmission.

⁷⁹ Directive 2006/116/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2006 on the term of protection of copyright and certain related rights (codified version).

⁸⁰ Directive 96/9/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 March 1996 on the legal protection of databases.

⁸¹ Directive 2001/84/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 September 2001 on the resale right for the benefit of the author of an original work of art.

⁸² Directive 2001/29/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 May 2001 on the harmonisation of certain aspects of copyright and related rights in the information society.

⁸³ Directive 2004/48/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 April 2004 on the enforcement of intellectual property rights.

⁸⁴ Directive 2012/28/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 on certain permitted uses of orphan Works.

⁸⁵ Directive 2014/26/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 February 2014 on collective management of copyright and related rights and multi-territorial licensing of rights in musical works for online use in the internal market.

It firstly states that authors should have exclusive right to authorise or prohibit direct or indirect, temporary or permanent **[1] reproduction** of their works by any means and in any form.⁸⁶ This right is considered to be the most basic economic right of an author.⁸⁷ Moreover, authors should have the exclusive right to authorise or prohibit any **[2] communication to the public** of their works, by wire or wireless means, including **[3] the right of making available to the public** of their works in such a way that members of that public may access them from a place and at a time individually chosen by them.⁸⁸ Finally, authors should have the exclusive right to authorise or prohibit any form of **[4] distribution** to the public by sale or otherwise of their works (either original or its copies). In that regard, such right should not be exhausted unless the first sale or other transfer of ownership in the EU is made by the owner or with his/her consent.⁸⁹

3.2.2.2. Exceptions & limitations

The ISD lists several exceptions to the exclusive rights of the copyright owner. Those exceptions can be applied in cases which do not conflict with a normal exploitation of the work and do not unreasonably prejudice the legitimate interests of the right holder (the so-called a three-step-test.)⁹⁰

The only **mandatory exemption** listed therein concerns temporary acts of reproduction which are transient or incidental and an integral and essential part of a technological process and whose sole purpose is to enable a transmission in a network between third parties by an intermediary or a lawful use of a work and which have no independent economic significance do not fall under the exclusive right of reproduction of the author of a work.⁹¹

The ISD lists a number of **optional exceptions** that Member States may introduce by their national legislation.⁹² The most relevant exception, for Made4You project, that concerns only the reproduction right is the reproduction for non-commercial purposes.⁹³ In such a case, the right holder does not have the exclusive right to authorise or prohibit the reproduction of work but he or she has to receive a fair compensation. With regards to the exceptions concerning both, the exclusive right of reproduction and the exclusive right of distribution, the ISD states that Member States may prescribe such exceptions in their domestic legislation for teaching and scientific research⁹⁴; and for a benefit of people with disability which are directly related to the disability and of a non-commercial nature to the extent required by the specific disability⁹⁵.

⁸⁶ Articles 1 and 2, Directive 2001/29/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 May 2001 on the harmonisation of certain aspects of copyright and related rights in the information society.

⁸⁷ Geiger C et.al., *The Information Society Directive*, p. 401. In: Stamataoudi I, Torremans P, *EU Copyright Law: A Commentary*, Elgar Commentaries 2014.

⁸⁸ Article 3, Directive 2001/29/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 May 2001 on the harmonisation of certain aspects of copyright and related rights in the information society.

⁸⁹ Ivi, Article 4.

⁹⁰ Ivi, Article 5(5) and Geiger C et.al., *The Information Society Directive*, p. 442. In: Stamataoudi I, Torremans P, *EU Copyright Law: A Commentary*, Elgar Commentaries 2014.

⁹¹ Ivi, Article 5(1).

⁹² In total, there are 20 optional exceptions that Member States could introduce into their domestic legislation.

⁹³ Ivi, Article 5(2)(b).

⁹⁴ Ivi, Article 5(3)(a).

⁹⁵ Ivi, Article 5(3)(b).

3.2.2.3. Directive 2006/116/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2006 on the term of protection of copyright and certain related rights (hereinafter: the TD)

In the EU and according to the basic rule of the TD, the term protection for literary and artistic works (within the meaning of Article 2 of the Berne Convention⁹⁶) shall run for the life of the author plus 70 years after his or her death.⁹⁷ For works of joint authorship, the 70-year period is calculated from the death of the last surviving author⁹⁸ while in the case of anonymous or pseudonymous works protection runs for 70 years after the work is lawfully made available to the public.⁹⁹ With regards to authors' **moral rights**, none of the EU Directives regulating copyright and related rights deals with this matter. However, all EU Member States are contracting parties to the Berne Convention which, in Article 6bis (2), prescribes that moral rights (paternity and integrity rights) shall, after author's death, be maintained at least until the expiry of the economic rights. Due to such a lack of harmonisation on the EU level, national regimes in this regard differ significantly.¹⁰⁰

3.3 Open Source Software

The term open source is sometimes used very broadly as any approach to one's intellectual property that entails a higher level of transparency or greater access to information than it is the case usually.¹⁰¹

A software is **free** if its users enjoy the four essential freedoms:

- The freedom **to run** the program as you wish, for any purpose (freedom 0).
- The freedom **to study** how the program works and **change it** so it does your computing as you wish (freedom 1). Access to the source code is a precondition for this freedom.
- The freedom **to redistribute** copies so you can help others (freedom 2).
- The freedom **to distribute copies of your modified versions** to others (freedom 3). By doing this you can give the whole community a chance to benefit from your changes. Access to the source code is a precondition for this.

⁹⁶ Article 2(1) of the Berne Convention: The expression "literary and artistic works" shall include every production in the literary, scientific and artistic domain, whatever may be the mode or form of its expression, such as books, pamphlets and other writings; lectures, addresses, sermons and other works of the same nature; dramatic or dramaticomusical works; choreographic works and entertainments in dumb show; musical compositions with or without words; cinematographic works to which are assimilated works expressed by a process analogous to cinematography; works of drawing, painting, architecture, sculpture, engraving and lithography; photographic works to which are assimilated works expressed by a process analogous to photography; works of applied art; illustrations, maps, plans, sketches and three-dimensional works relative to geography, topography, architecture or science.

⁹⁷ Article 1, Directive 2006/116/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2006 on the term of protection of copyright and certain related rights.

⁹⁸ Ivi, Article 1(2).

⁹⁹ Ivi, Article 1(3).

¹⁰⁰ Minero G, The Term Directive, p. 284. In: Stamataoudi I, Torremans P, EU Copyright Law: A Commentary, Elgar Commentaries 2014.

¹⁰¹ Hope J, Open Source Licensing. In *Intellectual Property Management in Health and Agricultural Innovation: A Handbook of Best Practices*. Available online.

3.3.1. Open vs. proprietary software

Open source software (i.e. Linux) represents an evolutionary process – by contributions coming from self-selected project participants who are subject to trial-and-error testing in diverse use environments whose results influence further development (so-called ‘the bazaar’ or ‘collective production’). Here, the software owner refrains from keeping the source code as a secret and grants an IP license to others so they can have the legal right to access and manipulate copyright-protected aspects of the code. For open source software development to work, its users and developers must be authorized to access the source code. By contrast, *conventional or proprietary software* is usually protected through IP rights (copyright, patent, trade secrets) which is used as a strategy to exclude some or all prospective users of the technology. The source code is treated as a trade secret and the original expression contained in the program’s source code is subject to copyright protection.

3.3.2. OSS license

Open source software license is a license that conforms to the latest definition given by the Open Source Initiative and only those licenses falling under such definition are legally allowed to carry a registered certification mark. Today, there are around 80 licenses approved by the OSI¹⁰² ¹⁰³ (*OSI approved*). The license governs exactly what companies and developers can do with the software they developed.

For a software to be considered open source, licensees must be free to:
use the software for any purpose (free redistribution).

make copies and distribute them without paying royalties to the licensor.

prepare derivative works and distribute them, also without paying royalties.

access and use the source code.

use the open source software in combination with other software (including proprietary).

An OSL cannot limit the number of products a licensee is allowed to distribute, the identity or geographic location of the recipients, or the price the licensee asks them to pay.

There are 2 main categories of open source licenses: academic or permissive and copyleft or restrictive.

Table 5: Academic license vs. Copyleft license

Academic license	Copyleft license
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Does not require users to make externally deployed improvements available to the licensor on the same terms as the original technology → such software can be used as part of programs distributed under other licenses (including proprietary) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Allow users to modify and redistribute a software program
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A company is allowed to use the code in proprietary software, with or without modifications 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The licensee is obliged to make all relevant downstream technologies available to all users under the

¹⁰² Onetti A, Verma S, Open Source Licensing and Business Model. Available online.

¹⁰³ Open Source Initiative: <https://opensource.org/>; Open Source Initiative’s list with OSI approved licences: <https://opensource.org/licenses/alphabetical>.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • same terms as provided by the original license
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Code (or its derived work) under the academic license can be re-licensed under a proprietary license, re-branded and commercialized by anyone (not only the original developer) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No one enjoys any special privilege with regards to any improvements
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In most cases, AL is used for a <i>core component of the solution</i> while revenues usually come from proprietary extension 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No one enjoys any exclusive rights to any improvements
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When licensor's primary goal is only to encourage widespread of the initial innovation because in such case, CLL may deter potential licensees who want to be able to commercialize their own improvements on a proprietary basis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CLL limit commercial adoption of a software → revenue does not originate from licensing fees
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Examples of the most popular ALs: MIT, Apache2.0, BSD, ISC 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A company adopting such licensing strategy, in addition to costs for providing customer support and professional services, also has to bear engineering and R&D expenses and investments
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The aim of CLL is to create an ever-growing pool of downstream innovations that remain freely accessible to all new users
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Examples of the most popular CLLs: GPL2.0; GPL3.0; AGPL3.0, LGPL

3.4 Creative Commons Licenses

Starting from the middle 80s, the traditional copyright model, based on the “all rights reserved” concept, was under revision by many scholars and practitioners.¹⁰⁴ An alternative copyright management model was found which enforced innovative licenses. Term ‘Creative Commons’ refers to both, the project itself and to the non-profit organization behind it. As a project, Creative Commons aims “to promote a global debate on new paradigms of copyright management and to defuse legal and technological tools (such as the licenses and all

¹⁰⁴ Aliprandi S, Creative Commons: A User Guide, Ledizioni, 2014, p. 11-18.

the services related), which can allow for a “some rights reserved” model in a cultural products distribution”.¹⁰⁵

A copyright license is a legal instrument by which the copyright holder decides on the use and distribution of her work. One of its main purposes is to authorize some kinds of use of the work which would not normally be allowed in the traditional – “all rights reserved” model. The application of a license on a work concerns the subsequent phase followed by the initial acquisition of copyright and the obtainment of a proof of authorship. In other words, **the author (the licensor) first automatically obtains the copyright for her work and then she decides on how to regulate her exclusive (copy)rights by applying a license on such work (the licensed work) whose effects (of such open-content license) are spread on variety of indeterminate subjects (the licensees).**

Writing a license is regulated under the civil law umbrella, more precisely contract law. Therefore, any author/owner of the work is entitled to write her own license and apply it to her work. However, poorly written license that does not contain important clauses or that is not clearly written would probably not perform its function properly. In order to avoid this issues, a licensor may decide to apply one of the standardized licenses that are released by specific non-profit organizations, such as Creative Commons, the Free Software Foundation, and the Apache Software Foundation.

Creative Commons licenses can be shaped in three different ways that have different legal importance: as a legal code, as a commons deed or as a digital code. **The legal code** is a license in its full meaning. It contains several preambles and articles by which the distribution of the licensed work is regulated. **The commons deeds** is a brief explanation of the license (i.e. of the legal code), written in a clear language and simply structured. Importantly, from a legal point of view, commons deed is not a license but simply a tool for understanding the legal code. It has no legal value and its content does not appear in the actual license – legal code. **The digital code** is metadata – data about data – a description of the license that can be understood by a computer program.¹⁰⁶

Table 6¹⁰⁷: From the licensor’s point of view ...

licensees are <u>required</u> ...	licensees are <u>allowed</u> ...
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> to get your permission to do any of the things you choose to restrict (e.g., make a commercial use, create a derivative work) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> to copy the work
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> to keep any copyright notice intact on all copies of your work 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> to distribute the work
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> to link to your license from copies of the work 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> to display or perform it publicly
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> not to alter the terms of the license 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> to make digital public performances of it (e.g., webcasting)

¹⁰⁵ Ivi, p. 11-18.

¹⁰⁶ Ivi, p. 19-36.

¹⁰⁷ Ivi, p. 19-36, paras. 22-25.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> not to use technology to restrict other licensees' lawful uses of the work 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> to shift the work into another format as a verbatim copy
--	--

Table 7¹⁰⁸: From the licensee's point of view, when you use any Creative Commons work ...

you must <u>always</u> ...	you must <u>never</u> ...
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> attribute the creator of the work 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> alter the terms of the license
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> get permission from the creator to do anything that goes beyond the terms of the license 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> use the work in any way that is prejudicial to the reputation of the creator of the work
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> keep any copyright notice attached to the work intact on all copies of the work 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> imply that the creator is endorsing or sponsoring you or your work
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> name the CC license and provide a link to it from any copies of the work 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> add any technologies (such as digital rights management) to the work that restrict other people from using it under the terms of the license
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> where you make changes to the work, acknowledge the original work and indicate that changes have been made 	

3.4.1. About CC licenses

Creative Commons licenses normally consist of two parts; in the first part, the owner indicates freedoms that she wants to allow with regards to her work. The licenses may, in the first part, contain following wording: *"You are free to Share – to copy, distribute and transmit the work"* or *"You are free to Remix – to adapt the work"*. The second part of the license explains in detail the conditions on which the licensed work may be used by licensees. It is widely accepted that there are 4 basic clauses which the licensor can choose:

1. **Attribution** – "You must attribute the work in the manner specified by the author or licensor (but not in any way that suggests that they endorse you or your use of the work).";
2. **Non Commercial** – "You may not use this work for commercial purposes.";
3. **No Derivatives** – "You may not alter, transform, or build upon this work.";
4. **Share Alike** – "If you alter, transform, or build upon this work, you may distribute the resulting work only under the same or similar license to this one."¹⁰⁹

By matching the four basic clauses there can be 6 Creative Common licenses, listed from the most permissive to the most restrictive¹¹⁰:

¹⁰⁸ Ivi, paras. 26-27.

¹⁰⁹ Aliprandi S, Creative Commons: A User Guide, Ledizioni, 2014, p. 19-36, paras. 28-40.

¹¹⁰ Descriptions and illustrations of the Creative Commons Licenses were taken from the website of Creative Commons. Available at: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/>.

- **Attribution**

This license lets others distribute, remix, tweak, and build upon your work, even commercially, as long as they credit you for the original creation. This is the most accommodating of licenses offered. Recommended for maximum dissemination and use of licensed materials.

- **Attribution-Share Alike**

This license lets others remix, tweak, and build upon your work even for commercial purposes, as long as they credit you and license their new creations under the identical terms. This license is often compared to “copyleft” free and open source software licenses. All new works based on yours will carry the same license, so any derivatives will also allow commercial use. This is the license used by Wikipedia and is recommended for materials that would benefit from incorporating content from Wikipedia and similarly licensed projects.

- **Attribution-No Derivatives**

This license allows for redistribution, commercial and non-commercial, as long as it is passed along unchanged and in whole, with credit to you.

- **Attribution-Non Commercial**

This license lets others remix, tweak, and build upon your work non-commercially, and although their new works must also acknowledge you and be non-commercial, they don't have to license their derivative works on the same terms.

- **Attribution-Non Commercial-Share Alike**

This license lets others remix, tweak, and build upon your work non-commercially, as long as they credit you and license their new creations under the identical terms.

- **Attribution-Non Commercial-No Derivatives**

This license is the most restrictive of our six main licenses, only allowing others to download your works and share them with others as long as they credit you, but they can't change them in any way or use them commercially.

For the sake of completeness, it is important to make a further distinction between *free cultural work* and *non-free cultural work*. **Free cultural works** are the ones that can be most readily used, shared, and remixed by others, and go furthest toward creating a commons of

freely reusable materials.¹¹¹ For example, work that is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution license or Attribution-Share Alike is considered as a free cultural work (together with anything else in the worldwide *public domain* marked with CC0 or with the Public Domain Mark). Hence, it can be concluded that other Creative Commons licenses allow more limited uses of the licensed work (and, therefore, works licensed under these licenses cannot be considered a free cultural work). According to Freedom Defined¹¹², to fall under the definition of a free cultural works, 4 requirements have to be fulfilled:

- the freedom **to use** the work and enjoy the benefits of using it,
- the freedom **to study** the work and to apply knowledge acquired from it,
- the freedom **to make and redistribute copies**, in whole or in part, of the information or expression,
- the freedom **to make changes and improvements**, and **to distribute derivative** works.

Free Culture Licenses must grant the following freedoms without limitations¹¹³:

- **The freedom to use and perform the work:** licensee is allowed to make any use, private or public, of the licensed work.
- **The freedom to study the work and apply the information:** licensee must be allowed to examine the licensed work and to use the knowledge gained from the work.
- **The freedom to redistribute copies:** licensee may sell, swap or give away the copies for free, as part of a larger work, a collection or independently.
- **The freedom to distribute derivative works:** the license does not limit the freedom to distribute a modified version, regardless of the intent and purpose of such modifications.

Additional conditions¹¹⁴:

- **Availability of source data:** when the final work has been obtained through the compilation of a source file or multiple source files.
- **Use of a free format:** for digital files, the format should not be protected by patents.
- **No technical restrictions:** no technical measures were used to limit the freedoms listed above.
- **No other restrictions or limitations:** such as contracts, privacy rights or similar.

Implications for Careables

Briefly, the whole process of technical documentation starts by forming multidisciplinary teams that engage in the design, development and prototyping processes. Each team creates a thorough understanding of the need and social context of the stakeholders which results in a prototype. The result of the first prototype is tested in a real-life setting. Ultimately, the new solutions are consequently documented. The main goal set by the Made4You Consor-

¹¹¹ <https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/public-domain/freeworks/>.

¹¹² <https://freedomdefined.org/Definition>.

¹¹³ <https://freedomdefined.org/Definition>.

¹¹⁴ <https://freedomdefined.org/Definition>.

tium is to publish documentation of various solutions designed for people with physical limitations in order to enable them, engineers, fabricators and designers to engage in collaborative work and to share technical designs, models, and software (hereinafter: the Careables). In order to exploit this goal to its fullest extent, such documentation should be as open as possible and with the minimum legal barriers for their free use and replication. Current technical documentations available in the world are either incomplete (which hardens the ‘DIY’ process) or are protected by copyright. The latter means that the author of a technical documentation (i.e. instructions on how to use the solution) enjoys exclusive rights to authorise or prohibit the reproduction of the solution, their communication and making them available to the public as well as their distribution to the public by sale or by other means. In practice, this would mean that anyone willing to reproduce the solution himself would have to request an authorization to do so from the author unless the Member State of the author implemented one or more optional exceptions under the ISD. Namely, anyone will be allowed to reproduce the solution where a Member State of the author allowed its reproduction for non-commercial purposes under the condition of providing a fair compensation to the author. Further on, anyone will be allowed to reproduce and/or distribute a solution if a Member State of the author implemented such exception for teaching and scientific purposes and/or for a benefit of people with disability which are directly related to the disability and of a non-commercial nature to the extent required by the specific disability. In order to understand whether one or more optional exceptions apply it is necessary to analyse the applicable laws of the Member States concerned on case-by-case basis. If that is the case, the documentation may be freely used in accordance with such exception. However, if there is no exception prescribed by the national law, it is important to have in place one of the licenses described above in order to enable further use and reproduction of the documentations and Careables.

3.5 Patent rights

Patents provide a legal protection upon an application for any invention, in any field of technology, provided that such invention is **new**, involves an **inventive step** and is capable of **industrial application**.¹¹⁵ If granted, inventor enjoys exclusive rights in preventing anyone from making, using, offering for sale, selling, or importing that product as well as the right to assign or transfer the patent and conclude licensing agreement, for a period of 20 years counted from a filing date. In order to enjoy these exclusive rights, the inventor has to disclose his invention in a manner that is sufficiently clear so that it can be carried out by a person skilled in the art.¹¹⁶

Table 8¹⁷: Patent vs. Copyright

Patent	Copyright
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Granted upon filing an application and after fulfilling certain requirements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Automatically granted

¹¹⁵ Article 27, Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS Agreement), available at: https://www.wto.org/english/docs_e/legal_e/27-trips.pdf.

¹¹⁶ See Articles 28, 29, 33, Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS Agreement), available at: https://www.wto.org/english/docs_e/legal_e/27-trips.pdf.

¹¹⁷ For further reading, see Skonieczka M, How open is Open Source Hardware?, KU Leuven master thesis, 2016.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fragmentary protection (only of novel and inventive parts of the work) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Protection of the work in its entirety
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High costs of patent application and lengthy procedure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No costs
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Territorial protection (fees have to be paid in every country where the application has been filed) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Protection across the Union (i.e. Berne Union)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exclusive rights granted to inventor 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exclusive rights granted to the author

3.6 Open Source Hardware

According to the definition given by Open Source Hardware Association, open source hardware is “a term for **tangible artefacts** — machines, devices, or other physical things — whose design has been released to the public in such a way that anyone can make, modify, distribute, and use those things”.¹¹⁸ This definition is based on definitions for open source software. However, “[h]ardware is different from software in that **physical resources must always be committed for the creation of physical goods**. Accordingly, persons or companies producing items (“products”) under an OSHW license have an obligation to make it clear that such products are not manufactured, sold, warrantied, or otherwise sanctioned by the original designer and also not to make use of any trademarks owned by the original designer”.¹¹⁹ A product that will be distributed under an open source hardware license has to respect the following criteria:

- **Documentation:** the hardware has to be released with documentation including design files and must allow modification and distribution of the design files. If the documentation is not furnished with the physical product, there should be a well-publicized means of obtaining this documentation for no more than a reasonable reproduction cost, preferably downloading via the Internet without charge.
- **Scope:** the documentation has to clearly state what exactly has been released under the license.
- **Necessary software:** if the licensed design requires embedded software in order to operate then the license may require meeting the one of the following conditions:
 - a. The interfaces are sufficiently documented to write open source software that allows the device to operate properly.
 - b. The necessary software is released under an approved Open Source Initiative license.
- **Derived works:** the license must allow for modifications and derived works. It shall also allow them to be distributed under the same terms as the license of the original work. **The license shall allow for the manufacture, sale, distribution, and use of products created from the design files, the design files themselves, and derivatives thereof.**

¹¹⁸ <https://www.oshwa.org/definition/>.

¹¹⁹ <https://www.oshwa.org/definition/>.

- **Free redistribution:** the license shall not restrict any part from selling or giving away the project documentation nor it shall require the royalty or other fee for sale of derived works.
- **Attribution:** the license may require that derived documents to provide attribution to the licensor when distributing design files, manufactured products and/or their derivatives. The license may further require this information to be accessible to the end-user using the device normally and it may also require that derived works carry a different name or a version number from the original work.
- The license **must not discriminate** against any person or a group.
- The license **must not restrict** anyone from making a use of the work in a specific field of endeavour.
- The license must apply to all to whom the work is redistributed without a need for execution of an additional license by those parties.
- The license must not be specific to a product. This means that the rights granted by the license must not depend on the licensed work being part of a particular product.
- The license must not place any restrictions on other products integrated with the licensed work but not being its derivative.
- The license must be technology neutral.

Implications for Careables

Copyright licenses (such as OSSL and CCL) cannot be applied to tangible products (i.e. on a hardware) as tangible products are not subject to copyright protection since they do not fall under the definition of literary and artistic works provided by the Berne Convention. However, a hardware usually consists of both, a tangible product and a design documentation describing how to build the product.¹²⁰ Therefore, the documentation will normally fall under the copyright protection and it may be, upon a decision of its author, distributed under one of the licenses described above. At the same time, a hardware component, created by using such documentation, does not fall under the same legal regime. There are two possible scenarios. In the first scenario, a person who obtained patent protection for innovative parts of a hardware may decide to apply an open source license to it. Depending on terms of license, others will be allowed to use and replicate freely. In the second scenario, a person may decide not to obtain a patent protection, in which case other will not need to request a permission to copy, modify or build upon a hardware. At the same time, this implies that a creator of the hardware cannot apply license to her work. Hence, when dealing with this matter, it is crucial to make a distinction between the design files for the hardware (i.e. the documentation) and the hardware itself. The design files are normally protected by copyright and their free use will depend on the will of the author to license the work or not. If the hardware itself is not protected by patent (which does not happen automatically as it is the case with copyright), anyone is allowed to manufacture the hardware without author's permission as long as they can do so without infringing the copyright attributed to the design files.

¹²⁰ Skonieczka M, How open is Open Source Hardware?, KU Leuven master thesis, 2016, pp. 24, 25.

4 Made4You, Careables and implications concerning Liability

4.1 Introduction

The present Section aims at analysing the possible implications that may arise under the perspective of liability concerning the co-design, development and reproduction of the many projects that are present on Careables. Before outlining the possible implications for the Careables stakeholders, a brief premise is necessary with regard to the concepts of **liability**, in its connection with **tort law** and **contract law** as well as the so-called '**duty of care**' and the '**strict liability**'. After such clarifications, an overview of liability in DIY environments for 'simple' devices is provided (section 4.2). Finally, section 4.3 outlines the main aspects of liability in the context of co-design and production of medical devices.

4.1.1. Contract law

Contract law is a specific branch of obligations law in civil law jurisdictions. A contract is an agreement between two or more parties to establish or regulate an economic relationship between them. A contract is binding among the contracting parties for the execution each of its obligation, predisposing specific forms of protection in case of non-compliance. The essential elements of a contract are typically defined by the law that is applicable to the same selves. Contracts are used for economic exchanges. An example of this may be represented by the transfer of copyright from an author to a publisher. Another kind of contract can be seen in purchase agreements, where a party (the seller) transfers the ownership of a good to another party (the buyer), which has to pay the price of such good.

4.1.2. Tort law

Tort law grants individuals that have been victims of a wrongdoing the right to action and remedies to be executed against the wrongdoer. The fundamentals of tort law go back until Roman law, which is a common ground from many law systems in Europe – particularly, for what concerns the so-called 'Lex Aquilia', which requires that **unintentional or negligent act causing an unjustified injury to another person obliges the person who has committed the act to pay the suffered damages**. The liability ascending from tort law differs from the one of contract law: the first follows when a subject violates not a specific duty (deriving from a pre-existing obligation) but a generic duty, that is usually indicated by the '*neminem laedere*' doctrine. In Common Law tradition, a tort is a civil wrong that unfairly cause losses or harms to someone. The tortfeasor, i.e., the person who commits the tort, results to be liable for the unfair act committed and the victim is entitled to bring civil legal action in order to determine the monetary costs to be paid by the tortfeasor. In order to analyse the concept of liability for the Careables context, two underlying elements are further outlined: 1) the notion of '**duty of care**', and 2) the notion of '**product liability**' and the correlated '**strict liability doctrine**'.

4.1.2.1. Tort law and the 'duty of care'

There is not a common framework in Europe concerning tort law. Tort law vary from law system to another and it is not always easy to find a 'basic rule' that may be seen as a 'fil rouge' for the identification of liability, fault and damage. For example, the French model is based on the notion of '*faute*' as the cause of the damage from which may derive the other

elements. German law (followed by the Portuguese and Austrian laws) follow a different model, for which the basic rule has to be found in the breach of absolute rights (e.g. property, life, health, etc.) even regardless of the occurrence of a damage.¹²¹

The Common law model, on the contrary seems to be close to the French model. In the light of the absence of a common framework in Europe concerning tort law, the Common Law model – similar in certain aspects to the French model – is taken into account for the explanatory purposes of the present section.

In Common law, the three most important criteria concerning the liability for **negligence** are: 1) the **duty of care**; 2) the **breach** of the duty of care; and 3) the **damage** (or injury) caused to the victim. Thus, an individual must breach a duty of care (against the victim) and damage has to be seen as a consequence, reasonably to be linked to the ‘negligent’ behaviour of the wrongdoer. In a known opinion by Lord Atkin in the ‘Donoghue vs. Stevenson’ case¹²², it is provided a clear outline of what may be conceived as duty of care: “You must take reasonable care to avoid acts or omissions which you can reasonably foresee would be likely to injure your neighbour. Who, then, in law, is my neighbour? The answer seems to be – persons who are so closely and directly affected by my act that I ought reasonably to have them in contemplation as being so affected when I am directing my mind to the acts or omissions which are called in question”.¹²³

4.1.2.2. *Tort law and the ‘negligence doctrine’*

The rule of duty of care is fundamental for understanding the *negligence doctrine*. In litigation, **in case of duty of care and negligence, the claimant has to demonstrate the negligence of the wrongdoer**. This **differs** for instance from another kind of liability, the so-called ‘**strict liability**’, for which victim has not to demonstrate the negligence of the person deemed to have caused the damage, as the liability is inferred *in re ipsa*. The rule of duty of care is a legal principle common both to civil law as well as to common law traditions and it represents a fundamental principle for ensuring a peaceful ‘living together’ in common environments.

4.1.2.3. *Tort law and the ‘strict liability doctrine’*

In civil law, **strict liability** is a standard of liability under which a person is legally responsible for the consequences **even in the absence of fault** of the wrongdoer.

In litigation, the claimant has **only to demonstrate that the tort occurred** and that the defendant is responsible. Strict liability is generally imposed by law to situations considered to be inherently dangerous. An example of strict liability is to be found in the field of **product liability**.

4.1.3. Product Liability Law

Product liability law can be conceived as a means to ensure on the one hand the safety of consumers and on the other hand, the insurance of an accountability chain of manufacturers, distributors, suppliers and all the actors involved in the production and sell of a given product. It aims at providing a redress for consumers that have been harmed by defective products.

¹²¹ See A. di Majo, Cap. I, Discorso generale sulla responsabilità civile, pp. 12-17, in N. Lipari e P. Rescigno, Diritto Civile, Vol. IV, Tomo III, 2009.

¹²² Donoghue v Stevenson [1932] A.C. 562, [1932] UKHL 100, 1932 S.C. (H.L.) 31, 1932 S.L.T. 317, [1932] W.N. 139.

¹²³ Ibid., 580 (Lord Atkin).

A general principle of product liability law relies on the idea that the party that has to be held liable is the 'strong party' of the relationship consumer-seller/producer/manufacturer. **Strict liability** is foreseen for the product manufacturer under product liability law. Such kind of liability rather than focussing on the behaviour of the manufacturer (which is the case when negligence is evaluated), it focus on the product itself. Thus, **under strict liability, the manufacturer is liable if the product is defective, even if the manufacturer was not negligent in making that product defective.**

4.2 DIY environments and DIY 'simple' devices

In the last year it became noticeable the growth of DIY communities and environments. Also, in legal literature the topic has started to be approached by researchers¹²⁴ and has been studied in the context of research projects, such as the 'DiDIY'– 'Digital Do it Yourself!' H2020 research project.¹²⁵

The context of DIY environments may be seen as a composition of a multitude of actors and stakeholders. Every actor of such an environment has its specific role and is attracted for different reasons that may range for practical to ethical ones. Actors may contribute for instance as mere designers, as makers, etc. One of the main questions that is often posed in such context concerns what liability may be each individual subject to that is involved in this 'creation chain'. This section tries to provide a brief outline of such liability paradigm.

Even though the Careables stakeholders may be more oriented to the co-creation of medical devices rather than simple 'objects'/'products'/'devices', the topic is of interest as it may represent a starting point to understand the liability framework and its key points.

4.2.1. What liability?

4.2.1.1. Manufacturing

(Strict) Product liability...

Scholars and researchers have been questioning whether product liability law applies in the context of DIY objects/products/devices. The issue has been studied under comparative lenses and perspectives in order to find the applicable rationales.¹²⁶

One of the first assumptions that have to be done once questioning what kind of liability stems for DIY stakeholders with regards to product liability law, concerns the fact that product liability law's *ratio* is grounded on the idea that products are normally manufactured and sold to consumers by producers that are very often big entities. Hence, product liability law stems from the view that it exists a centred and vertical relationship between big entities/producers and individuals/consumers. With respect to DIY environments, however, this may not always be the case. Accordingly, it has been argued the production of DIY devices challenge product

¹²⁴ N. Freeman Engstrom, 3d Printing and Product Liability: Identifying the Obstacles, *University of Pennsylvania Law Review Online*, 162 (35), 2013; N. D. Berkowitz, Strict Liability for Individuals? The Impact of 3d Printing on Products Liability Law, *Washington University Law Review*, 92(4), 1019 – 1053, 2015; H. Nielson, Manufacturing Consumer Protection for 3d Printed Products, *Arizona Law Review*, 57(2), 609-622, 2015, L. Osborn, Regulating Three Dimensional Printing: The Converging Worlds of Bits and Atoms, *San Diego Law Review*, 51, 553-621, 2014.

¹²⁵ See DiDiY, <http://www.didiy.eu/>, particularly D6.1 – 'Dominant legal challenges and solutions practiced' (hereinafter: 'D6.1').

¹²⁶ See e.g. A. Daly, *Regulating Revolution: An Introduction to 3D Printing and the Law* (May 22, 2016). *Socio-Legal Aspects of the 3D Printing Revolution*, Palgrave, 2016.

liability laws, and that the new context of production of such kind of objects blurs the hierarchical dichotomy provided by product liability law between producers and consumers.¹²⁷ In a legal deliverable of the DiDIY research project a practical example is provided that may be of help in order to better depict this aspect. It concerns the manufacturing of an object by a non-professional maker:

“At a request of a friend, a hobbyist maker produces a spare part of an object commonly used in a household: a lounge chandelier arm. It is designed reusing design files that were shared by another designer through an online design sharing platform through CAD software adapting it by another friend, a design passionate, and produced with the maker’s 3D printer. After some time, the spare part proves defective and causes the fall of the chandelier itself hurting one of the children of the maker’s friend. Who is liable for this accident? Who made mistakes and might be held liable to pay damages? The point is that the 3D printer itself, the parts and materials chosen by the maker to build it, or the way the printer is assembled, maintained and used, may all be other reasons why the final product proves defective, even if the CAD design was perfect.”¹²⁸

The evaluation of this case requires to go back to the notions of product liability law, strict liability and negligence, as outlined in the sections above.

Typically, **product liability law** foresees as standard rule the application of the **strict liability doctrine** for producers.

- US product liability law for instance, foresees that “one engaged in the business of selling or otherwise distributing products who sells or distributes a defective product is subject to liability for harm to persons or property caused by the defect”, without having to carry the burden of proof of the negligence in the production of the defective product.
- In the EU context, the product liability rule is quite similar to the US context. The majority of Member States legislations foresee the rule of **strict liability** for defective products.¹²⁹

This set of rules seems to be, however, **more orientated to a entities ‘in course of business’** – concerning the US context – or **‘industrially’** oriented – concerning the EU context¹³⁰ (which may not be the primarily case for DIY stakeholders).

Moreover, Art. 7(c) of the Product Liability Directive¹³¹ states that **‘producers’ may not be held liable** (in the sense and for the effects outlined by the Product Liability Directive) **if he or**

¹²⁷ Ivi, p. 68.

¹²⁸ Ivi, p. 22.

¹²⁹ EU framework on Product liability is based on the Product Liability Directive. The EU framework has been translated in national legislations by Member States and therefore requirements in every national context may vary. For an overview on this, see M. Felwick, V. Kenyon, E. Martin, The product liability regime in the EU, 25 October 2018, available at: <https://www.lexology.com/library/detail.aspx?g=a7d00949-5e0e-4941-ad02-95dde3de4b70>, last accessed: 4/12/2018.

¹³⁰ See recitals of Product Liability Directive, particularly when stating: “Whereas liability without fault should apply only to movables which have been industrially produced”.

¹³¹ Council Directive 85/374/EEC of 25 July 1985 on the approximation of the laws, regulations and administrative provisions of the Member States concerning liability for defective products.

she proves “that the product was neither manufactured by him for sale or any form of distribution for economic purpose nor manufactured or distributed by him in the course of his business”.

Again, factors as ‘course of business’ and ‘economic purposes’ are underlined as limit for the application of strict liability. This exception to strict liability may be applicable to DIY makers, but there are no specific published case laws on this issue.¹³²

...or duty of care?

According to some scholars¹³³, “the theory underlying the imposition of strict product liability is threefold: (1) those who manufacture and sell products tend to be enterprises; (2) imposing liability on enterprises is fair because those who profit from the risk should bear the costs of accidents; and (3) enterprises are better than injury victims at absorbing and distributing losses”. With regard to this assumption, it has to be noted, that the DIY environment does not reflect the illustrated conditions: 1) DIY makers usually are amateurs, and normally they are not professionals or companies; 2) usually, DIY makers do not perceive profits for the manufacturing of their physical object; nonetheless 3) the produced physical object may imply harms or damages to individuals. To this regard, it has been argued that **“home-made products could fall outside the scope of strict liability”**¹³⁴ and that “a simple **negligence standard** may be more equitable depending on the circumstances because the majority of these sellers are small, sole proprietorships”.¹³⁵ However, it has been also noted that strict liability rules could be applied on specific cases, depending when an entity is a regular seller, rather than an occasional or casual one.¹³⁶ Finally, concerning liability in general for DIY stakeholders some have questioned what social part should be protected. “Individual initiative of those who tend to explore an innovative technological field or the legal protection of the final product user? It can happen that in some cases the two figures – amateur producer and final consumer – coincide, but the opposite may happen”.¹³⁷ However, going back to the DiDIY example of the chandelier arm, it should be underlined that **in litigation there could be involved many defendants according to the different roles that are played by the people involved in the manufacturing process**.¹³⁸ Therefore, concerning the DIY environments, it should be noted that as a general rule (to be evaluated on a case-by-case basis) liability for defective products is to be applied only when the defendant is ‘in the course of business’ or the ‘products are industrially produced’.¹³⁹ It remains clear that, on the contrary, when a duty of care is breached, than it is the case for tort law (duty of care/negligence) liability.

¹³² See also DiDIY, D6.1, p.23.

¹³³ H. Nielson, Manufacturing Consumer Protection for 3d Printed Products, Arizona Law Review, 57(2), 609-622, 2015.

¹³⁴ DIY, D.6.1, p. 22.

¹³⁵ H. Nielson, Manufacturing Consumer Protection for 3d Printed Products, Arizona Law Review, 57(2), 609-622, 2015, p. 617.

¹³⁶ Ibid.

¹³⁷ Ibid.

¹³⁸ S. Wang, When Classical Doctrines of Products Liability Encounter 3D Printing: New Challenges In The New Landscape, Houston Business and Tax Law Journal, 104, p. 111.

¹³⁹ The interpretation of this concepts is all but clear. For more critical views, see A. Daly, Regulating Revolution: An Introduction to 3D Printing and the Law (May 22, 2016). Socio-Legal Aspects of the 3D Printing Revolution, Palgrave, 2016, p. 68.

4.2.1.2. Design

Concerning the design of products, analogously to what affirmed above, a distinction should be made between professional and non-professional designers: professional makers may be treated under strict liability rules, while both the non-professional figure and non-commercial seller of “print-at-home” may be more likely held liable only in case of negligence, under the duty of care.¹⁴⁰

4.2.1.3. Warrant Defects

Other observations are as well important to underline: the effects of inappropriate use shall be borne only by the consumer and manufacturers should provide appropriate warnings and instructions on the use of the product itself.¹⁴¹

4.3 DIY environments and Medical Devices

The case of DIY environments is interesting for what concerns the case of the production and manufacturing of Medical Devices. But the first and most important assumption that has to be made here is that what has been outlined above represents a different hypothesis with respect to the production of the so called ‘Medical Devices’.

4.3.1. DIY and objects falling under the definition of ‘Medical Devices’

Legal literature concerning the production of DIY physical products in the field of health care has been less numerous than DIY ‘simple’ products as such. Nonetheless, there have been some notable academic contributions¹⁴² as well as projects and/or initiatives in the field.¹⁴³ Particularly, the UBORA project has aimed at creating Open Source Medical Devices (‘OSMD’) designed following collaborative strategies in order to help reduce the costs for the development of medical devices, to boost innovation across the EU and Africa. Such collaborative strategies were enacted through the sharing of ideas and concepts, design files, documentation, source data, with other professional medical device designers.

As already noted in the dissemination context of such project, “open movement prizes innovation, creativity and ingenuity more than compliance to rules and standards, which are not often fully known and valued and should be considered from the beginning of the development process.”¹⁴⁴ **When the sharing of knowledge, documentation, experience, instructions concerns objects that may fall under the definition of medical devices as provided by the Medical Devices legal framework, then the compliance to rules and standards foreseen by law and Regulations is a must.**

In the context of the Careables platform, Consortium partners should:

¹⁴⁰ Ibid.

¹⁴¹ A. Harris, Acting as the consumer and manufacturer, the user must accept the responsibilities of both parties, *Journal of Science Policy & Governance*, 2015, p. 6.

¹⁴² A. Daly, *Regulating Revolution: An Introduction to 3D Printing and the Law* (May 22, 2016). *Socio-Legal Aspects of the 3D Printing Revolution*, Palgrave, 2016.

¹⁴³ See for the ‘e-Nable’ initiative (<http://enablingthefuture.org/>) or ‘UBORA’ (<http://ubora-biomedical.org/>).

¹⁴⁴ C. De Maria, L. di Pietro et al., Safe innovation: On medical device legislation in Europe and Africa, *Health Policy and Technology* 7 (2018) 156 – 165, p. 162.

- ✓ Preliminarily evaluate what kind of ‘devices’ the projects that will be made available on Careables are: whether they are to be considered as ‘medical devices’ or not;
- ✓ Once evaluated this first aspect, partners may evaluate to establish compliance procedures for the design and co-creation of medical devices on Careables in compliance to applicable standards and legislations.

4.3.2. The legal framework concerning Medical Devices

4.3.2.1. *The current framework on Medical Devices*

The basic legal framework in Europe that aims at ensuring a high level of quality of medical devices and to guarantee the protection of human health and safety is actually composed by three Directives (Council Directive 90/385/EEC on Active Implantable Medical Devices¹⁴⁵, Council Directive 93/42/EEC on Medical Devices¹⁴⁶ and Council Directive 98/79/EC on In Vitro Diagnostic Medical Devices¹⁴⁷). These directives set the legal requirements to meet before medical devices can be put on the market. When medical devices are marketed, CE mark has to be provided as a proof of certification, even if there is the possibility to bear self-certification in certain cases. **Medical devices** are defined as any equipment used to treat, diagnose or prevent disease and they range from basic equipment such as syringes, needles and blood pressure monitors through to anaesthetic equipment, surgical instruments, health pacemakers, hip prostheses, MRI scanners.¹⁴⁸ The approach proposed by MDD is based on the following principles: i) the harmonization has to be limited to essential requirements and ii) only products presenting the essential requirements can be put on the market. The Directives foresee four categories of devices (I, IIa, IIb and III) in dependence of the risks they may have for patients. Criteria taken into consideration for this classification are based on the following elements: invasiveness of the device, intended duration of its use, whether the device is active or passive, etc. Devices are classified by the Directive as follows:

- ✓ **Low risk devices** (category I): the manufacturer is allowed to put a CE mark and registers the product with a national competent authority, a system of self-certification. The national agencies have the power to audit whether the manufacturer has complied with legal requirements.
- ✓ **High-risk devices** (class II and III): their marketing is controlled through so called Notified or Conformity Assessment Bodies (i.e. standards organizations designated in each Member State by the relevant Authority. These Notified Bodies check the development and the designs of the device.

The Directives are further specified by standards and relevant Bodies provide guidance through different documentation. Standards are elaborated by the European Standards Group (CEN) and many are subsequently adopted or incorporated into international standards by the ISO (International Standards Organization); guidance documents (e.g. ‘MEDDEV’

¹⁴⁵ Council Directive of 20 June 1990 on the approximation of the laws of the Member States relating to active implantable medical devices (90/385/EEC).

¹⁴⁶ Council Directive 93/42/EEC of 14 June 1993 concerning medical devices.

¹⁴⁷ Directive 98/79/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 October 1998 on in vitro diagnostic medical devices.

¹⁴⁸ See D. B. Jefferys, The regulation of medical devices and the role of the Medical Devices Agency, British journal of clinical pharmacology, vol. 52, no 3, 2001, p. 230.

documents) are issued by the European Medical Device Expert Group at the European Commission. Similar mechanisms are provided by Directives concerning implantable devices and in vitro diagnostics.

4.3.2.2. *The reform of Medical Devices framework*

The framework concerning Medical Devices has been recently reformed. The Medical Devices Directives were in need of modernization as it seemed they no longer reflecting the scientific and technological progress and at the same time seemed too focused on the route towards CE-marking and not enough on sufficient controls to ensure safety and effectiveness.¹⁴⁹ The three current Directives have been replaced by two new Regulations: Regulation (EU) 2017/745 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on medical devices¹⁵⁰ – incorporating active implantable medical devices – and Regulation (EU) 2017/746¹⁵¹ of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on in vitro diagnostic medical devices. These two regulations have been adopted on 5 April 2017, entered into force on 25 May 2017. The Regulation on medical devices will be directly applicable for all EU Member States in spring 2020, whereas the Regulation on in vitro diagnostic medical devices will be directly applicable as of spring 2022.

Innovations of the renewed framework...

In its press-release after the adoption in the EU Parliament of the final texts on 5 April 2017, the European Commission enumerated the many benefits ascending from the renewed framework, which are both for patients and consumers as well as for manufacturers of medical devices. As highlighted by the EC, the new framework contains many elements of innovation:¹⁵²

- stricter ex-ante control for high-risk devices *via* a new pre-market scrutiny mechanism with the involvement of a pool of experts at EU level;
- the reinforcement of the criteria for designation and processes for oversight of Notified Bodies;
- the inclusion of certain aesthetic devices which present the same characteristics and risk profile as analogous medical devices under the scope of these Regulations;
- the introduction of a new risk classification system for *in vitro* diagnostic medical devices in line with international guidance;
- improved transparency through the establishment of a comprehensive EU database on medical devices and of a device traceability system based on Unique Device Identification;
- the introduction of an “implant card” containing information about implanted medical devices for a patient;
- the reinforcement of the rules on clinical evidence, including an EU-wide coordinated procedure for authorisation of multi-centre clinical investigations;
- the strengthening of post-market surveillance requirements for manufacturers;

¹⁴⁹ See G. Verhenneman, Medical Devices Regulations sound the legal future for heart valves and sticking plasters, 06 June 2018, in CiTiP Blog, available at: <https://www.law.kuleuven.be/citip/blog/medical-devices-regulations-sound-the-legal-future-for-heart-valves-and-sticking-plasters/>, last accessed: 04/12/2018.

¹⁵⁰ Regulation (EU) 2017/745 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on medical devices, amending Directive 2001/83/EC, Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 and Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 and repealing Council Directives 90/385/EEC and 93/42/EEC.

¹⁵¹ Regulation (EU) 2017/746 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on in vitro diagnostic medical devices and repealing Directive 98/79/EC and Commission Decision 2010/227/EU.

¹⁵² See EC website, Growth > Sectors > Medical Devices> Regulatory Framework, available at: https://ec.europa.eu/growth/sectors/medical-devices/regulatory-framework_en, last accessed: 4/12/2018.

improved coordination mechanisms between EU countries in the fields of vigilance and market surveillance.

More importantly, the reforms tried to address one of the issues with the old framework, concerning the scope of medical devices. The new medical devices regulations aim at reducing the uncertainty the previously concerned the medical device scope in general. Both Regulations contain clear definitions on the different kinds of medical devices such as “custom-made device”, “active device”, or “invasive device”. Moreover, the concept of “intended purpose” has been further specified.

... more safety implies more burdens.

The increase of safety, control, transparency and harmonization implies a price that not everyone – especially little stakeholders – may easily bear. Among all, costs for conformity will be higher following the new procedures. Micro and small organizations may benefit from favourable conditions – concerning financial coverage for manufacturers, the person responsible for regulatory compliance and the fees charged by notified bodies – however the higher costs might imply that certain smaller players to encounter more difficulties in putting devices in the market.¹⁵³

4.3.3. What Liability?

4.3.3.1. Manufacturing

The rationale behind Medical Devices legislations envisages the existence of a **centric manufacturer** and supplier of devices to be marketed. Analogously to what observed for DIY environments for ‘simple’ products, **the fact that a Medical Device may be designed and produced on a decentralised basis** (i.e. through the Careables platform) **challenges this kind of assumption**. The notion of ‘*manufacturer*’ has been defined by EU Directives. According to Art. 1(2)(f) of the Medical Devices Directive (‘MDD’), the manufacturer is: “the natural or legal person with responsibility for the design, manufacture, packaging and labelling of a device before it is placed on the market under his own name, regardless of whether these operations are carried out by that person himself or on his behalf by a third party”. In order to better understand such definition it may of help to analyse also the notion of ‘placing on the market’, which is provided under Art. 1(2) of the MDD and “means the first making available in return for payment or free of charge of a device other than a device intended for clinical investigation, with a view to distribution and/or use on the Community market, regardless of whether it is new or fully refurbished”.

The key elements of these legal provisions concern the following elements:

- ✓ The operations of ‘designing, manufacturing, packaging and labelling a device’;
- ✓ The placement of a device on the market (in return of payment or for free);
- ✓ The placement in the market under the own name of the legal or natural person having responsibility of the above mentioned operations.

¹⁵³ See G. Verhenneman, Medical Devices Regulations sound the legal future for heart valves and sticking plasters, 06 June 2018, in CiTiP Blog, available at: <https://www.law.kuleuven.be/citip/blog/medical-devices-regulations-sound-the-legal-future-for-heart-valves-and-sticking-plasters/>, last accessed: 04/12/2018.

- ❖ Whereas and inasmuch the Careables platform does not ‘put devices on the market’ in the meaning of the MDD – even for free – under its own name, it may not be seen as (and therefore not be subject to the obligations to be burdened as) a manufacturer.
- ❖ Occurring the contrary, if the platform would place devices on the market, for free or against the payment of a price, and moreover under its own name, then the Careables platform might be qualified as manufacturer and therefore subject to the obligations foreseen by applicable legislation concerning Medical Devices.¹⁵⁴

4.3.3.2. From product liability to the duty of care

Analogously to what observed above (§4.2), the types of liabilities that may be associated to the different actors within the MDD framework may extend from product liability to negligence liability. Thus, **the following kinds of liability may apply in the context of Medical Devices**^{155 156}:

- **Product liability**

The same observations for **producers** in a ‘non-business’ context may apply, also for what concerns the single individual who produces a ‘product’ (i.e.: ‘producers’ may not be held liable if they prove “that the product was neither manufactured by him for sale or any form of distribution for economic purpose nor manufactured or distributed by him in the course of his business”¹⁵⁷). However, it is to be noted what already underlined above, that a **case-by-case** approach should be adopted: **strict liability rules could be applied** on specific cases, depending when an entity is a regular seller, rather than an occasional or casual one.

- **Negligence liability**

as analogously outlined above, occurring the above mentioned criteria (duty of care; the breach of such duty, and the damage caused by that breach) negligence liability may also apply. In this scenario, the **possible actors intervened in the process of creation** e.g. Careables itself, maker(s) that created the device, designer(s), as well as any medical professionals that have been involved for the production of the medical device, may **be held liable**.

The rules that have been outlined above are intended as general and limited to EU level legislations. It is to be noted that the main aspects outlined above concerning liability of manufacturers, designers, and other subjects involved may vary depending on national Member

¹⁵⁴ For observations concerning the possibility for a platform to be considered as manufacturer under EU medical device laws, see A. Daly, *Regulating Revolution: An Introduction to 3D Printing and the Law* (May 22, 2016). *Socio-Legal Aspects of the 3D Printing Revolution*, Palgrave, 2016, p. 76. The case in exams concerns the e-NABLE platform, see <http://e-nable.org/>.

¹⁵⁵ See W. Rehmann, D. Heimhalt, *Product Liability for Medicines and Medical Devices in the European Union*, in *TaylorWessing*, March 2016, available at: <https://united-kingdom.taylorwessing.com/synapse/ti-eu-medical-product-liability.html>, last accessed: 4/12/2018.

¹⁵⁶ See also M. Crosato, *Il quadro normativo attualmente vigente nel settore dei Dispositivi Medici*, Padova, 7 luglio 2015.

¹⁵⁷ Art. 7(1)(c) of the Product Liability Directive.

States' legislations and soft law implementing the Medical Devices European and Product Liability frameworks as well as soft law and decisions adopted by national Courts. Finally, in this context there have been analysed the main aspects of liability ascending by (general EU) civil and tort law. However, it is worth to note that **criminal liability** may be also implied in the context of creation and manufacturing of medical devices. Criminal law provisions vary as well from one Member State to another.¹⁵⁸

5 Ethical Guidelines

5.1 Introduction

This chapter supplements the previous ones by taking into a consideration ethical principles that need to be thought of while developing Careables. Ethical guidelines can be used as a support for relevant stakeholders to ensure wellbeing of individual, general wellbeing of the society, public health and security. "Ethical considerations can play a part in system governance by shaping the actions of people, imposing constraints and providing guidelines for the development and design of technology. The law provides the formal regulatory setting in which individuals, third parties, and institutions carry out their activities. However, **ethical guidelines provide a basis for the law, normative resources for the interpretation of the law and guidance that is sometimes additional to what the law requires**".¹⁵⁹

5.2 Fundamental moral principles

Ethical guidance relevant here can be based on 4 moral principles of autonomy, beneficence, non-maleficence, and justice. The four principles, generally accepted in Western tradition are studied in-depth in Beauchamp and Childress's Principles of Biomedical Ethics¹⁶⁰ and adapted from the International Medical Informatics Association ethical guidelines. The four fundamental principles of biomedical ethics are following¹⁶¹:

- *Respect for Persons and Autonomy*

All persons have a fundamental right to self-determination. Incorporates at least two ethical convictions: first, that individuals should be treated as autonomous agents, and second, that persons with diminished autonomy are entitled to protection. In its new formulation Personal autonomy refers to self-governance, to "self-rule that is

¹⁵⁸ An example among all may be provided by taking into account the application art. 43 of the Italian Criminal Code, which concerns crimes punished for 'fault' or negligence' and defines the cases in which an event shall be otherwise attributed to the offender as a consequence of his act or omission. "è colposo, o contro l'intenzione quando l'evento, anche se preveduto, non è voluto dall'agente e si verifica a causa di negligenza o imprudenza o imperizia, ovvero per inosservanza di leggi, regolamenti, ordini o discipline" (Art. 43(1) of the Italian Criminal Code).

¹⁵⁹ Verhenneman G, Vedder A, WITDOM, D6.1 – Legal and Ethical framework and privacy and security principles, p. 39, 2015, available at: <http://www.witdom.eu/deliverables>.

¹⁶⁰ Beauchamp TL, Childress JF, Principles of Biomedical Ethics, Oxford University Press, 2013; IMIA, Ethics for Health Informatics Professionals, The IMIA Code, its Meaning and Implication, 2016, available at: <https://imiamedinfo.org/wp/imia-code-of-ethics/>.

¹⁶¹ As described in Verhenneman G, Vedder A, WITDOM, D6.1 – Legal and Ethical framework and privacy and security principles, p. 39, 2015, available at: <http://www.witdom.eu/deliverables>.

free from both controlling interference by others and from limitations, such as inadequate understanding, that prevent meaningful choice.” “The principle [of respect for autonomy] can be stated as a negative obligation and as a positive obligation. As a negative obligation, autonomous actions should not be subjected to controlling constraints by others. As a positive obligation, this principle requires respectful treatment in disclosing information and fostering autonomous decision-making.

- *Principle of Justice*

All persons are equally entitled to a same degree of moral concern and attention. This does not mean that they should be treated completely equally as they may have different needs and vulnerabilities. It means however that they at least should be treated with the same procedural fairness. A broadly shared conception of justice and fairness is non-discrimination which opposes unequal treatment on the basis of properties or circumstances deemed morally irrelevant to the case at stake.

- *Principle of Beneficence*

All persons have a duty to advance the good of others and of themselves where the nature of this good, such as their vital health and security interests, is in keeping with the fundamental and ethically defensible values of the affected party and where advancing their good does not entail disproportionate harm to oneself.

- *Principle of Non-Maleficence*

All persons have a duty to prevent harm to other persons to the degree that it lies within their power to do so without undue harm to themselves. It underlies the Hippocratic maxim of the ‘*Primum non nocere*’: “Above all [or first] do no harm”. This principle refers to the duty to refrain from causing harm: “One ought not to inflict evil or harm” where a harm is defined as an adverse effect on one’s interest.

A secondary principle of responsibility may be derived from the four moral principles described above.¹⁶²

- *Responsibility*

According to this principle, whoever has an obligation based on the basic moral principles or originated from a specific social or professional role or function has a duty to fulfil that obligation to the best of her/his ability. The principle encompasses responsibilities for actions or consequences of actions of agents.¹⁶³

¹⁶² Vedder A, Responsibilities for Information on the Internet. In Himma KE, Tavani HT (Eds.), *The Handbook of Information and Computer Ethics*, 2009, pp. 339-359, New Jersey: John Wiley and Sons.

¹⁶³ Verhenneman G, Vedder A, WITDOM, D6.1 – Legal and Ethical framework and privacy and security principles, p. 40, 2015, available at: <http://www.witdom.eu/deliverables>.

5.3 Ethical issues addressed through and beyond the legal framework

5.3.1. A brief introduction

“Informational privacy can be defined as an individual’s right to determine whether, what, when, by whom and for what purpose personal information is collected, accessed, used or disclosed”.¹⁶⁴ Many legal instruments at various levels of applicability ensure high level of individual’s privacy and personal data. This can be seen in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the European Convention on Human Rights, the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, General Data Protection Regulation, current e-Privacy Directive 2002/58/EC as well as in the laws of EU Member States. However, no matter how comprehensive the laws applicable to protection of personal data are, they will never be able to fully protect individuals in all of the relevant aspects since the possibilities for ethically undesirable events will always remain present due to enforcement burdens.

5.3.2. Examples of ethical issues addressed through the legal framework

Current *concept of autonomy* is connected to concepts of individuality and identity. Nowadays, data about individuals is being collected and processed from multiple sources in order to provide more complete but anonymized datasets. However, problems of identifiability occur more regularly when several datasets are combined, hence, the question of anonymity becomes obvious. At the same time, currently applicable legislation (such as GDPR) does not protect personal data once it has been anonymized or expressed in an aggregated form. Therefore, “a new normative category of privacy protection based on privacy and ethical considerations must be established to protect individuals from misuses of their personal data in aggregated form”.¹⁶⁵ In parallel, the principle of the respect of autonomy may be practically implemented by using informed consent since it aims at safeguarding individual’s right to authorize usage of his/her personal data.¹⁶⁶ Further on, the international law of human rights states that people should be secure, free and protected. This principle may be expanded to *dignity* which addresses “a range of questions reflecting different types of personal needs that can contribute to sense of self or empowerment through technology”.¹⁶⁷ In practice, when personal data are treated as a positive asset made available, discoverable and meaningful, it strengthens dignity, drives economic opportunity and improves individual’s quality of life.

5.3.3. Examples of ethical issues addressed beyond the legal framework

Use of the ethical guidelines may be twofold. On the one hand, they may be used to increase the level of protection of human rights. On the other hand, they may be used to assess risks and benefits of tangible forms of harm (i.e. harm to health) and to prevent drawbacks and

¹⁶⁴ Ivi, p. 41.

¹⁶⁵ Vedder A, Responsibilities for Information on the Internet. In Himma KE, Tavani HT (Eds.), *The Handbook of Information and Computer Ethics*, 2009, pp. 339-359, New Jersey: John Wiley and Sons.

¹⁶⁶ Verhenneman G, Vedder A, WITDOM, D6.1 – Legal and Ethical framework and privacy and security principles, p. 42, 2015, available at: <http://www.witdom.eu/deliverables>.

¹⁶⁷ Ivi, p 42.

benefits that may not be quantifiable. For example, the *principle of justice* may be violated by public disclosure of information concerning person being diagnosed with cancer who may be latter charged with a higher insurance premium. Although the law already took into consideration these issues, the system can further implement protections based on categories beyond personal data and enforce global privacy assurance mechanisms.¹⁶⁸ Moreover, the *principle of non-maleficence* requires the use of technology in a way that mankind could benefit from it and to prevent harm to human beings, other living creatures, environment, etc. Hence, this principle is a useful tool for assessing safety of the project. Further on, the principle of beneficence requires following: “1) Protect and defend the rights of others; 2) Prevent harm from occurring to others; 3) Remove conditions that will cause harm to others; 4) Help persons with disabilities; 5) Rescue persons in danger”.¹⁶⁹

6 Conclusions

Purpose of the deliverable D6.1 was to provide a legal and ethical inventory of the applicable requirements and to provide an advice to the Made4You Consortium partners of their timely implementation from the early stage of the platform development. Hence, with regards to data protection and privacy laws, some of the main findings concern anonymization and security of personal data that will be processed, notion of (joint) controllers and processors, data minimization, accuracy and storage limitation principles as well as the overarching accountability principles. Further on, a clear distinction has been made between the key data protection legal requirements and recommendations that concern the Made4You research project, on the one hand, and those that concern Careables.org platform, on the other hand. Moreover, in-depth analysis has been done with regards to copyrighted and patented DIY technical documentation and products. As opposed to the traditional IP systems, alternative systems of open source software, open source hardware and creative commons have been analysed since the platform aims to map those DIY products that will be available to anyone who wishes to use them anywhere in the world. As many DIY products will be co-designed and reproduced, liability framework concerning (non) medical devices was inspected. It has been concluded that if the platform would place devices on the market, for free or against the payment of a price, and moreover under its own name, then the Careables platform might be qualified as manufacturer and therefore subject to the obligations foreseen by the applicable legislation concerning medical devices. Finally, fundamental principles of biomedical ethics have been studied in order to provide support to stakeholders to ensure wellbeing of individual and general wellbeing of the society and public health.

KU Leuven will, within the WP6 and during the next Consortium face-to-face meeting, further provide Consortium partners with the training on the main legal and ethical requirements distilled in this deliverable in order to pragmatically guide them, to contribute to, and to ensure their prompt and correct implementation. This exercise will be used to tailor drafting of the specific guidelines in D6.2 that will meet the specific needs of the maker communities and the patients/end-users involved in the co-creation process. Finally, this process will result in

¹⁶⁸ Ivi, p 43.

¹⁶⁹ Verhenneman G, Vedder A, WITDOM, D6.1 – Legal and Ethical framework and privacy and security principles, p. 44, 2015, available at: <http://www.witdom.eu/deliverables>.

the production of a set of practical legal guidelines which distinguish between technical requirements and organizational requirements and which allow to establish role-based responsibilities in the maker community.

7 Bibliography

- Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS Agreement)
- Aliprandi S, Creative Commons: A User Guide, Ledizioni, 2014
- Beauchamp TL, Childress JF, Principles of Biomedical Ethics, Oxford University Press, 2013
- Berkowitz, N. D., Strict Liability For Individuals? The Impact Of 3D Printing On Products Liability Law, Washington University Law Review, 92(4), 1019 – 1053, 2015.
- Berne Convention for the Protection of Literary and Artistic Works (as amended on September 28, 1979)
- Cavoukian, A., Privacy by design: the 7 foundational principles, Information and privacy commissioner of Ontario, 2009.
- CNIL, Privacy Impact Assessment (PIA), Methodology, February 2018 edition, available at: <https://www.cnil.fr/sites/default/files/atoms/files/cnil-pia-1-en-methodology.pdf>, last accessed: 4/12/2018
- Council Directive of 20 June 1990 on the approximation of the laws of the Member States relating to active implantable medical devices (90/385/EEC).
- Crosato, M., Il quadro normativo attualmente vigente nel settore dei Dispositivi Medici, 7 luglio 2015, Padova.
- Daly, A., Regulating Revolution: An Introduction to 3D Printing and the Law (May 22, 2016). Socio-Legal Aspects of the 3D Printing Revolution, Palgrave, 2016.
- De Maria, C., L. di Pietro et al., Safe innovation: On medical device legislation in Europe and Africa, Health Policy and Technology 7 (2018) 156 – 165.
- DiDiY, D6.1 – ‘Dominant legal challenges and solutions practiced’.
- Directive 2009/24/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 April 2009 on the legal protection of computer programs (Codified version) (Text with EEA relevance).
- Directive 2006/115/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2006 on rental right and lending right and on certain rights related to copyright in the field of intellectual property (codified version).
- Council of Europe (CoE), Convention for the Protection of Individuals with regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data.
- Council Directive 85/374/EEC of 25 July 1985 on the approximation of the laws, regulations and administrative provisions of the Member States concerning liability for defective products.
- Council Directive 93/83/EEC of 27 September 1993 on the coordination of certain rules concerning copyright and rights related to copyright applicable to satellite broadcasting and cable retransmission.
- Directive 2002/58/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 July 2002 concerning the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in the electronic communications, OJ L201 (hereinafter: ‘e-Privacy Directive’).
- Directive 2006/116/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2006 on the term of protection of copyright and certain related rights (codified version).
- Directive 96/9/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 March 1996 on the legal protection of databases.
- Directive 98/79/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 October 1998 on in vitro diagnostic medical devices.
- Directive 2001/84/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 September 2001 on the resale right for the benefit of the author of an original work of art.

- Directive 2001/29/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 May 2001 on the harmonisation of certain aspects of copyright and related rights in the information society.
- Directive 2004/48/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 April 2004 on the enforcement of intellectual property rights.
- Directive 2012/28/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 on certain permitted uses of orphan Works.
- Directive 2014/26/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 February 2014 on collective management of copyright and related rights and multi-territorial licensing of rights in musical works for online use in the internal market.
- Directive 95/46/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 October 1995 on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data
- Di Majo, A., Cap. I, Discorso generale sulla responsabilità civile, pp. 12-17, in N. Lipari e P. Rescigno, Diritto Civile, Vol. IV, Tomo III, 2009.
- EC, Horizon 2020 Programme. Guidance. How to complete your ethics self-assessment, Version 6.0, 23 July 2018.
- EC, Options for strengthening responsible research and innovation. Report of the expert group on the state of the art in Europe on responsible research and innovation, 2013.
- EDPS, Opinion 1/2015, Mobile Health, Reconciling technological innovation with data protection, 21 May 2015.
- EDPS, Opinion 5/2018, Preliminary Opinion on privacy by design, 31 May 2018.
- FRA, Handbook on European data protection law, 2018 edition.
- Freeman Engstrom, N., 3D Printing and Product Liability: Identifying the Obstacles, *University of Pennsylvania Law Review Online*, 162 (35), 2013.
- Geiger C et al., *The Information Society Directive*, p. 401. In: Stamataoudi I, Torremans P, *EU Copyright Law: A Commentary*, Elgar Commentaries 2014.
- Harris, A., Acting as the consumer and manufacturer, the user must accept the responsibilities of both parties, *Journal of Science Policy & Governance*, 2015.
- Hope J, Open Source Licensing. In *Intellectual Property Management in Health and Agricultural Innovation: A Handbook of Best Practices*.
- IMIA, *Ethics for Health Informatics Professionals, The IMIA Code, its Meaning and Implication*, 2016, available at: <https://imia-medinfo.org/wp/imia-code-of-ethics/>.
- Jefferys, D. B., The regulation of medical devices and the role of the Medical Devices Agency, *British journal of clinical pharmacology*, vol. 52, no 3, 2001.
- Minero G, *The Term Directive*, p. 284. In: Stamataoudi I, Torremans P, *EU Copyright Law: A Commentary*, Elgar Commentaries 2014.
- Nielson, H., Manufacturing Consumer Protection for 3D Printed Products, *Arizona Law Review*, 57(2), 609-622, 2015.
- OECD Guidelines on the Protection of Privacy and Transborder Flows of Personal Data, 2018.
- Onetti A, Verma S, Open Source Licensing and Business Model.
- Osborn, L., Regulating Three Dimensional Printing: The Converging Worlds Of Bits And Atoms, *San Diego Law Review*, 51, 553-621, 2014.
- PRIPARE, *Privacy- and Security-by-Design Methodology Handbook*, V1.00, 31 December 2015.
- Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council concerning the respect for private life and the protection of personal data in electronic communications and repealing Directive 2002/58/EC, COM(2017) 10, 10 January 2010.
- Rehmann, W., Heimhalt, D., Product Liability for Medicines and Medical Devices in the European Union, in *TaylorWessing*, March 2016, available at: <https://united-kingdom.taylorwessing.com/synapse/ti-eu-medical-product-liability.html>, last accessed: 4/12/2018.

- Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European parliament and of the council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation).
- Regulation (EU) 2017/745 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on medical devices, amending Directive 2001/83/EC, Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 and Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 and repealing Council Directives 90/385/EEC and 93/42/EEC.
- Regulation (EU) 2017/746 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on in vitro diagnostic medical devices and repealing Directive 98/79/EC and Commission Decision 2010/227/EU.
- Treaty on European Union and the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union, 2012/C 326/01.
- Tryggvadottir R, *European Libraries and the Internet: Copyright and Extended Collective Licenses*, KU Leuven Centre for IT&IP Law Series, 2018.
- Ubertazzi B, *The Principle of Free Movement of Goods: Community Exhaustion and parallel imports*, p. 38. In: Stamataoudi I, Torremans P, *EU Copyright Law: A Commentary*, Elgar Commentaries 2014
- Skonieczka M, *How open is Open Source Hardware?*, KU Leuven master thesis, 2016.
- Wang, S., *When Classical Doctrines of Products Liability Encounter 3D Printing: New Challenges In The New Landscape*, *Houston Business and Tax Law Journal*, 104.
- WP29, *Advice paper on special categories of data ("sensitive data")*, April 2011.
- WP29, *Annex to Letter from the WP29 to the European Commission, DG CONNECT on mHealth*, 5 February 2015.
- WP29, *Guidelines on consent under Regulation 2016/679*, WP259, adopted on 28 November 2017 as last revised and adopted on 10 April 2018.
- WP29, *Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) and determining whether processing is "likely to result in a high risk" for the purposes of Regulation 2016/679*, WP248 rev.01, adopted on 4 April 2017 as last revised and adopted on 4 October 2017.
- WP29, *Guidelines on transparency under Regulation 2016/679*, WP260 rev.01, adopted on 29 November 2017 as last revised and adopted on 11 April 2018.
- WP29, *Opinion 1/2010, on the concepts of "controller" and "processor"*, WP169, Adopted on 16 February 2010.
- WP29, *Opinion 4/2007 on concept of personal data*, WP136, adopted on 20 June 2007.
- WP29, *Opinion 5/2014 on Anonymisation Techniques*, WP216, 10 April 2014.
- WP29, *Opinion 06/2014 on the notion of legitimate interests of the data controller under Article 7 of Directive 95/46/EC*, WP217, adopted on 9 April 2014.
- WP29, *Working Document 02/2013 providing guidance on obtaining consent for cookies*, WP208, adopted on 2 October 2013.
- Van Alsenoy, B., *Allocating responsibility among controllers, processors and "everything in between": the definition of actors and roles in Directive 95/46/EC*, in *Computer Law & Security Review* 28 (2012) 25 – 43.
- Vedder A, *Responsibilities for Information on the Internet*. In Himma KE, Tavani HT (Eds.), *The Handbook of Information and Computer Ethics*, 2009, pp. 339-359, New Jersey: John Wiley and Sons.
- Verhenneman, G., *Medical Devices Regulations sound the legal future for heart valves and sticking plasters*, 06 June 2018, in *CiTiP Blog*, available at: <https://www.law.kuleuven.be/citip/blog/medical-devices-regulations-sound-the-legal-future-for-heart-valves-and-sticking-plasters/>, last accessed: 04/12/2018.
- Verhenneman G, Vedder A, WITDOM, D6.1 – **Legal and Ethical framework and privacy and security principles**, p. 39, 2015, available at: <http://www.witdom.eu/deliverables>.

Annex I - Inventory of key data protection principles and guidelines

The present Inventory foresees general legal requirements that Made4You Consortium partners have to take into account throughout the research project and for the development of the Careables platform. As illustrated above (see §2.6.2), legal principles and guidelines that will be further developed in D6.2, where – with particular regard to the development of Careables – these will be further operationalised.¹⁷⁰ Objective of this Inventory is therefore to preliminarily orient and guide the Consortium partners through a synthetic but effective canvas containing the key data protection principles and guidelines to be followed throughout the project.

Principle	Main legal source	Subject	Guideline / General Description
Lawfulness	Art. 6 GDPR	Legal basis for the processing of personal data	The processing of personal data can only take place if covered by a 'legal basis'. For each processing, the controller must evaluate which lawful basis is the most appropriate.
Lawfulness	Art. 6 GDPR WP259	Consent – Lawful acquisition	If identified as adequate legal basis, the acquisition of consent should occur in a lawful way. Consent must be: i) freely given ii) specific, iii) informed, and where applicable, iv) explicit.
Lawfulness	Art. 6 GDPR, WP259	Consent – Information	In order to be 'informed' adequate information should be provided when personal data is directly collected from the data subjects, so that they are able to make a free, specific and knowledgeable choice.
Lawfulness	Art. 6 GDPR, WP259	Consent – Management	A record of the data subjects' provision of consent should be kept (e.g. it should be maintained information concerning the session in which consent was expressed as well as the consent workflow; it should be kept a record of what kind of information was provided to individuals).

¹⁷⁰ These Guidelines are inspired by the PRIPARE Methodology. See PRIPARE, Privacy- and Security-by-Design Methodology Handbook, V1.00, 31 December 2015, Annex B – List of Privacy Principles, Guidelines, Criteria for Requirements Operationalization.

			Mechanisms for demonstrating that data subjects have provided consent should be evaluated and adopted.
Lawfulness	Art. 6 GDPR, WP259	Consent – Withdraw	Data subjects should be put in the condition to withdraw their consent in an easily and swift way.
Lawfulness	Art. 9 GDPR	Consent – Explicit	When sensitive data are processed, then data subject’s explicit consent is required.
Purpose limitation	Art 5(1)(b) GDPR	Purpose determination	The controller must define the purposes of data processing before the processing activity is started.
Purpose limitation	Art 5(1)(b) GDPR	‘Specific, explicit and legitimate purpose’	The purpose of the processing of personal data must be specified, explicated and legitimate. The specific purpose of personal data collected must be disclosed to data subjects.
Purpose limitation	Art 5(1)(b) GDPR	Further processing	The further processing of personal data for additional, specified purposes may occur in a manner that is compatible with the original purpose.
Storage limitation	Art 5(1)(e) GDPR	Storage of personal data	Data should be stored for a period no longer than necessary for the purpose of the processing. To this extent, the following measures may be taken into consideration: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The definition of a data retention policy, disciplining the necessary amount of time/criteria for the retention of personal data; - The definition of the action to be taken after the identified period of retention has expired –whether to anonymise or erase the data
Data minimization	Art. 5(1)(c) GDPR	Minimise the use of personal data	The processing of personal data should be limited to what is necessary to achieve a legitimate purpose. In other words, the use of personal data in its whole lifecycle should tend to be avoided or minimised. When feasible, the controller should use anonymisation techniques. If this is not possible, the controller may adopt further measures, such as pseudonymisation.
Accuracy	Art 5(1)(d) GDPR	Data accuracy	The controller should always put in place measures in order to: (1) check the accuracy of data; (2) record its source; (3) rectify data when not accurate or up-to-date.

Fairness	Art. 5(1)(a)	Fair processing of personal data	The controller must ensure that the processing of personal data occurs in a transparent manner. Processing activities should not be put in place secretly: individuals have the right to know how and which personal data are collected, used or otherwise processed, as well as aware of the risks, safeguards and their rights concerning the processing.
Transparency	Art. 5(1)(a), Rec. 39	Transparent processing of personal data	The processing of personal data should be transparent to natural persons that personal data concerning them are collected, used, consulted or otherwise processed and to what extent the personal data are or will be processed.
Transparency	Art. 13 GDPR, WP260	Information to data subjects	The controller must ensure that data subjects are provided with relevant information concerning the processing. (Additionally, the law requires specific contents to be disclosed to individuals: see Art. 13 GDPR). Such information may be provided – depending on the scope and context of the processing – e.g. within a Privacy Notice, or a Privacy Policy.
Transparency	Artt. 13, Rec. 39 GDPR	Right to information	When data is not obtained with the direct intervention of the data subjects, but e.g. by the intervention of third parties, then there should be provided adequate information to data subjects.
Transparency	Artt. 13-14 GDPR	Data subjects' rights	Under data protection legislation, data subjects rights are: right to be informed, right to access, right to rectification, right to erasure, right to restrict processing, right to data portability, rights in relation to automated decision making and profiling. Where applicable, controllers should ensure the possibility that data subjects may easily exercise their rights. Data subjects must also be informed over the possibility of exercising their rights and the consequences of exercising them.
Transparency	Artt. 15-21 GDPR	Data subjects' rights	Data subjects must also be informed over the possibility of exercising their rights and the consequences of exercising them.
Accountability	Art. 5(2) GDPR, Art. 26 GDPR	Documentation	All privacy and data protection practices, policies, procedures should be documented and all operations performed with personal data should be recorded.

Accountability	Art. 29 GDPR	Training	Awareness of persons in charge of the processing acting on behalf of the controllers may be strengthened through awareness initiatives (e.g. trainings, informative documents to be made available, etc.).
Accountability	Art. 5(2), Art. 24 GDPR	Governance	Controllers may evaluate to establish organisation privacy governance programmes.
Accountability	Artt. 24-26 GDPR	Establishment of data protection roles	When putting in place data processing activities, it is recommended the prior individuation and regulation of data protection roles and responsibilities among the many actors.
Accountability	Art. 28 GDPR	Processors and Sub-processors	Controllers should identify all subjects carrying out processing activities on behalf of them. The choice of processors must be accountable. Once identified, controllers shall ensure that these provide adequate guarantees for the compliance with data protection laws and as well that they will comply with obligations set by contracts/agreements.
Accountability	Art. 25 GDPR	Data protection by design	The adoption of a data protection by design is a key element in this project, especially for what concerns the development of the Careables platform. Controllers must ensure that privacy and data protection are take into account as of the early stages of the project.
Accountability	Art. 30 GDPR	Records of processing activities	Controllers must maintain record of the processing activities carried out under their responsibility and must provide it to the DPA when required.
Security of the processing	Art. 32 GDPR	Risk-based approach	There shall be implemented appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure a level of security appropriate to the risk. Organisations should adopt a 'risk based approach' in order to evaluate what kind of measures can better ensure the protection of individuals fundamental rights and freedoms. As suggested in Art. 32 GDPR, controllers and processors may take into consideration as appropriate measures to put in place: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- the anonymisation or encryption of personal data- the ability to ensure the ongoing confidentiality, integrity, availability and resilience of processing systems and services

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the ability to restore the availability and access to personal data in a timely manner in the event of a physical or technical incident - a process for regularly testing, assessing and evaluating the effectiveness of technical and organisational measures for ensuring the security of the processing. <p>The list is merely exemplificative, organisations should adopt the measures they deem suit best their specific context.</p>
Security of the processing	Art. 35 GDPR	DPIA	Organisations have to carry out a data protection impact assessment for processing activities likely to result in a high risk.
Security of the Processing	Art. 33-34 GDPR	Breach of personal data	<p>Controllers must be prepared in case a data breach occurs.</p> <p>For instance, a policy in case of data breach may be established. The data breach policy may provide, <i>inter alia</i>, instructions to persons in charge of the processing concerning the actions required, the cases when it will be necessary to notify the breach to the DPA, as well as communicate the same to data subjects.</p>

Annex II – Report of Data Protection Impact Assessments carried out in the context of Made4You

Introduction

In the context of Made4You project, Consortium partners have – in line with the legal requirement foreseen under Art. 35 GDPR – evaluated the opportunity to carry out Data Protection Impact Assessments with respect to the processing activities planned to be carried out during the project. As already illustrated above (§2.5.5.4), a Data Protection Impact Assessment should be carried out when the processing is “likely to result in a high risk for the rights and freedoms of natural persons” (Art. 35(1) GDPR). In particular, WP29¹⁷¹ recommends the execution

¹⁷¹ WP29, Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) and determining whether processing is “likely to result in a high risk” for the purposes of Regulation 2016/679, WP248 rev.01, adopted on 4 April 2017 as last revised and adopted on 4 October 2017.

of DPIA when specific circumstances occur. To this end, WP29 lists ‘nine criteria’¹⁷² to take into account in order to establish whether to carry out a DPIA. Consortium partners have deemed that two out of the nine criteria listed by WP29 may occur for the purposes of the Made4You project, and particularly:

- ‘Data concerning vulnerable data subjects’: part of the activities carry out by Consortium partners imply the processing of personal data of subjects to be considered as ‘vulnerable’ (e.g. people having health care needs, minors, patients, elderly, etc.);
- ‘Sensitive data or data of highly personal nature’: as also (an more in-depth) outlined above (§2.5.1) in order to achieve the results of the research project Consortium partners may carry out processing activities on individuals’ personal and sensitive data (and particularly, data concerning health).

An additional observation has to be provided for the DPIA concerning ‘Careables’ platform, for which the execution of a DPIA was of further importance inasmuch it concerned the development thereof. Moreover and not less importantly, the execution of DPIAs has been carried out by Consortium partners in order to overall demonstrate accountability with respect to the activities to be put in place throughout the project, as well as commitment to the principle of data protection by design as enshrined in Art. 25 GDPR.

Selected Methodology and Tools

In order to reach homogeneous results, Consortium partners adopted a common approach with respect to tools and methodology for the execution of Data Protection Impact Assessments. In particular, Consortium partners have:

- adopted the Methodology provided by the French Data Protection Authority ‘CNIL’ (‘Commission Nationale de l’Informatique et des Libertés’);¹⁷³
- carried out their respective DPIAs through the software/tool ‘PIA’, rendered available by the same CNIL on its website.¹⁷⁴

Main findings and results

¹⁷² Ivi, pp. 9-13.

¹⁷³ CNIL, Privacy Impact Assessment (PIA), Methodology, February 2018 edition, available at: <https://www.cnil.fr/sites/default/files/atoms/files/cnil-pia-1-en-methodology.pdf>, last accessed: 4/12/2018.

¹⁷⁴ See CNIL, CNIL publishes and update of its PIA Guides, 26 February 2018, available at: <https://www.cnil.fr/en/cnil-publishes-update-its-pia-guides>, last accessed: 4/12/2018.

According to WP29, the DPIA is an **assessment** of the impact of the processing for the rights and freedoms of the data subject. On the basis of Art. 35(7) GDPR, a Data Protection Impact Assessment must contain:

- a description and purposes of the processing of personal data;
- an evaluation of the necessity and proportionality of the processing operations in relation to the purposes;
- an assessment of the risks to the rights and freedoms of data subjects;
- the measures envisaged to address the risks, including safeguards, security measures and mechanisms to ensure the protection of personal data and to demonstrate compliance with the GDPR.

These elements are met by the CNIL's Methodology, which propose the above outlined content under the following sections:

1. 'PIA Information: In this section controllers provide the general details concerning the processing and the DPIA that has to be executed;
2. 'Context': In this section is established 'the context' and is provided an overview of the processing of personal data to be assessed;
3. 'Fundamental principles': In this section each controller is required to execute an assessment over the necessity and proportionality of the processing;
4. 'Controls to protect the personal rights of data subject': this section is aimed at illustrating the main measures that controllers put in place to ensure the protection of data subjects' rights;
5. 'Risks': where each controller must assess of the risks to the rights and freedoms of the data subjects;
6. 'Action Plan': It contains a description of the further measures to address the risks;
7. 'Risks overview': It provides a table concerning the risks, potential threats, sources, and measures adopted for the processing of personal data.
8. 'Risks mapping': A 'risk matrix' is shown therein, on the basis of the assessment carried out in the preceding sections.

In line with the principle of accountability foreseen by art. 5(2) GDPR, Consortium Partners have duly documented Data Protection Impact Assessments. The DPIA documentation drafted by each Consortium Partner has been shared within the Consortium through the project platform 'ZDI'.

In order to foster trust for the processing operations carried out in the context of M4Y, as well as to show accountability and transparency towards individuals and public authorities, herein below are summarised the main findings and results of the executed DPIAs.

Consortium partners having carried out a DPIA	Each of the following partners has carried out a DPIA: → WAAG, OPEN, GIG, MAKEA, WEV, TOG.
Description and purposes of the processing of personal data	Each partner has defined and described the purposes of the processing of personal data. Consortium partners has described the assessed processing activities in relation with the scope of the research project (e.g. Processing of data subjects personal data for the participation to ‘Meet-Ups’ and ‘Open Days’; Processing of personal data of participants to dissemination events or co-design events, etc.), as well as related to the processing of personal data for the purposes of the development of the Careables platform.
An evaluation of the necessity and proportionality of the processing operations in relation to the purposes;	The evaluation of necessity and proportionality of each processing activity has been executed under the section ‘Fundamental principles’ of each DPIA. First, Consortium partners have determined whether the processing purposes are specified, explicit and legitimate. Second, Consortium partners have assessed the lawful basis of the processing. On the basis of partners’ respective evaluations, consent results the primary/most frequent ground used for the assessed processing activities. Furthermore, Consortium partners also provided information over data accuracy, data minimisation, and the intended storage of personal data. Concerning the latter topic, is to be noted that generally, Consortium partners indicated that the period of retention of personal data is coinciding with the end of the project.
An assessment of the risks to the rights and freedoms of data subjects;	Consortium partners have carried out an assessment of the risks to the rights and freedoms of data subjects under. Most part of the assessments show a negligible risk. A minor part of these find a limited risk.
The measures envisaged to address the risks , including safeguards, security measures and mechanisms to ensure the protection of personal data and to demonstrate compliance with the GDPR.	Consortium partners have evaluated the measures envisaged to address the risks. Hereby are reported some of the envisaged measures: anonymisation, encryption, data partitioning, logical access control, traceability (logging), data minimisation, password, operating security, backups, archiving, paper document security, privacy and data protection policies.

Careables.org

